

Extending electric bus charging infrastructure considering charging scheduling and energy pricing

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ABSTRACT

The transition to fully electrified public transport is a pivotal step towards sustainable urban mobility. However, the efficient deployment of charging infrastructure poses significant challenges, particularly in optimizing charger placement to meet operational and economic constraints. This article introduces a novel strategic planning model designed to calculate the optimal locations for extending an existing charging station network that supports the daily operations of an electric bus fleet. The planning model is a bi-objective mixed integer-linear program that considers both the operational needs of the fleet operator and the energy pricing schema as imposed by energy management authorities. By accounting for parameters such as charging station installation costs, Time-of-Use tariffs and peak demand charges, the model addresses an integrated planning problem with two objectives: the minimization of the monetary cost required for the operation of the bus fleet and the buses' deadhead times. An implementation in a network using data from Manhattan, New York and a case study in Limassol, Cyprus, demonstrate the model's efficacy in providing actionable insights for urban planners and transport authorities, ensuring cost-effectiveness and reduced environmental impact.

1. Introduction

The transition to electric mobility is needed now more than ever. While the adoption of several types of Electric Vehicles (EV) has increased over the last few years, EV adoption deviates between different cities, countries and transport domain sectors (Anastasiadou and Gavanas, 2022). In the context of public transport, there is an ongoing movement of electrifying vehicle fleets that support the public transport services, with bus fleets being the focal point of this transition over the last years (Kruchina, 2023).

One of the primary drivers behind the electrification of public transport fleets is the urgent need to reduce Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions and combat climate change. According to the European Environment Agency¹, transport accounts for nearly 25% of the EU's greenhouse gas emissions, with road transport being the largest contributor. To meet the demands of urbanization, public transportation systems – particularly those relying on diesel-powered bus fleets – contribute their share to urban air pollution through increased service levels. Therefore, transitioning to electric buses offers a promising solution to mitigate these environmental impacts while sustaining the same service levels for the residents of the urban environment (Kazemzadeh et al., 2022).

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¹ Greenhouse gas emissions from transport in Europe by the European Environment Agency, [Website](https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/press-releases/2023/04/14)

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In response to these challenges, several initiatives and legislative frameworks have been established to promote the adoption of cleaner public transport. The European Green Deal² aims to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050, emphasizing the reduction of emissions from the transport sector. The Fit for 55 package³, introduced as part of this broader strategy, sets an ambitious target to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. Additionally, the Clean Bus Declaration Act, signed in 2016 by over 80 private and public organizations, serves as both a commitment and a blueprint to procuring zero-emission buses, further accelerating the shift towards sustainable urban mobility towards 2030 (Lu et al., 2023).

Despite these initiatives, the transition to electric mobility introduces significant technical complexities, particularly in planning the refueling infrastructure for electric buses. A critical challenge in this context is the optimal placement of charging stations, which must account for the availability of various potential sites within the urban landscape. While multiple criteria can guide this decision, the most common priority is to minimize deadheading distances, ensuring buses can access charging stations seamlessly without unnecessary travel. This challenge extends beyond spatial considerations; it also encompasses temporal dimensions, requiring integrated decisions about charger locations and scheduling the charging times of electric buses. Furthermore, the selection of charger types for each location adds another layer of complexity. These decisions are further complicated by the interplay between the operational needs of the bus fleet and external constraints, such as energy pricing structures and the distribution capacity limits imposed by energy management authorities.

Amid these complex challenges, adopting scientific planning approaches is essential for effectively managing the transition to electric bus fleets. Digital transport models and mathematical programming can provide decision support regarding optimizing routes, reducing operational costs, and maintaining high service levels throughout this shift. While the international community has increasingly recognized and adopted digital modeling in urban transport planning (Bastarrianto et al., 2023), one may claim that adopting such digital tools in practice is not yet successful in several parts of the world. Even if this lag in adoption can be attributed to several factors, enhanced utilization of such tools could provide the necessary evidence to motivate policymakers and stakeholders to accelerate the shift towards sustainable urban transportation.

The work presented in this study aims to provide a novel mathematical programming model that can support strategic planning for the extension of an already existing charging station network that supports the daily operation of an electric bus fleet. The model focuses on the integrated problem of charging station location and bus charging scheduling while accounting for monetary costs that emerge from energy pricing. As shown in the latter sections of this article, the proposed model does not only provide a single optimal scenario for the extension of the charging station network under study, but it can provide multiple solutions that are optimal concerning two objectives: (i) the buses deadhead times, and (ii) the total monetary cost for the installation of new chargers and the daily electricity consumption.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on the Charging Station Location Problem (CSLP) and adjacent problems. Section 3 presents our methodology and mathematical formulation of the problem. Section 4 provides the numerical experiment results for two case studies. The article concludes with a summary of remarks and a proposal for future research directions.

2. Literature review

This section reviews recent research and methodologies on the wider topic of planning electric bus charging infrastructure. While the term encompasses various types of equipment and systems, this review primarily focuses on the problem of selecting charging station locations (CSLP) for electric bus fleets (Section 2.1). Additionally, it explores related challenges, including the integration of CSLP with the electric bus charging scheduling problem (Section 2.2) and the incorporation of energy grid considerations (Section 2.3).

2.1. The charging station location problem for electric bus lines networks

Early efforts in this domain, such as the work by Jang et al. (2016), introduced a mixed-integer programming model focused on minimizing the initial costs of charging infrastructure. Their model aimed at identifying the number of stationary chargers at terminal stops and the optimal bus battery sizes. Similarly, Wang et al. (2016) presented integer linear programming models to place chargers at terminals and bus stops, accompanied by heuristics to manage problem complexity.

Kunith et al. (2017) presented a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model that determined both optimal charging station placements and suitable battery capacities for each bus line. In the work by Bi et al. (2018), the authors developed a multi-objective framework for placing wireless chargers within a multi-route electric bus system. This study considered system-level costs alongside life cycle greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption, utilizing a genetic algorithm (GA) to resolve the optimization model and evaluate the trade-offs between installation and lifecycle costs.

In 2019, two notable research articles on the CSLP were published, each offering valuable insights into the problem. Although both studies incorporate considerations related to energy consumption and the energy grid, they do not yet address the charging scheduling sub-problem. He et al. (2019) propose a MILP model to minimize costs associated with vehicle batteries, fast-charging stations, energy storage systems, and electricity demand charges, while Lin et al. (2019) introduce a mixed-integer nonlinear

² The European Green Deal, [Website](#)

³ The Fit-for-55 package, [Website](#)

programming (MINLP) model that framed the problem of sizing and locating plug-in charging stations for electric buses as a multi-stage planning model.

Recent studies have continued to refine approaches to the CSLP. Both [Wu et al. \(2021\)](#) and [He et al. \(2023\)](#) examine station deployment, including fast chargers, and considering factors such as the monetary cost of transitioning from conventional to electric bus fleets. Although neither explicitly models charging scheduling, both propose novel solution methods: [Wu et al. \(2021\)](#) develops a two-stage nonlinear programming model, while [He et al. \(2023\)](#) introduces a bi-objective MINLP. Of the two, only [He et al. \(2023\)](#) computes Pareto-optimal solutions based on bi-objective formulation.

2.2. The integrated problem of charging station location and charging scheduling

To handle the complexity of the integration of the CSLP with the charging scheduling sub-problem, several studies employ heuristic approaches that are able to provide optimized (but not fully optimal solutions). Starting with the work of [Liu and Ceder \(2020\)](#), the authors investigate the vehicle scheduling problem for battery electric transit vehicles. Assuming fixed charger locations and a predetermined service schedule, they propose a dual-framework model to optimize charging strategies, with the objective of minimizing both the fleet size and the number of required chargers. Other connected studies are the ones by [Li et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Yao et al. \(2020\)](#), where the authors both employ Genetic Algorithm (GA)-based methods to address, respectively, the joint optimization of electric bus scheduling and station placement and the Multi-Depot Electric Vehicle Scheduling Problem with heterogeneous fleets. [Stumpe et al. \(2021\)](#) also use a heuristic Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS)-based algorithm to solve a MILP model for simultaneous optimization of opportunity charging infrastructure and scheduling across three German transit networks.

In 2022 and 2023, several more significant contributions were made. [Olsen and Kliewer \(2022\)](#) explored the integration of depot charging planning and electric bus scheduling using a VNS algorithm to minimize overall costs, including depot charger installation, vehicle expenses, and operational costs. [Hu et al. \(2022\)](#) addressed uncertainties in passenger demand and travel times by presenting a robust optimization model for optimizing the location of en-route fast chargers and charging schedules under varying electricity prices and waiting costs. Additionally, [He et al. \(2022\)](#) developed a MILP model to optimize charger deployment, onboard battery capacity, and charging schedules concurrently. They introduced a charging scheduling model and applied a rolling horizon approach to optimize real-time charging schedules for electric buses. [Wang et al. \(2022\)](#) contributed by developing a MILP model for opportunity charger deployment and bus scheduling, determining optimal battery capacity, fleet size, charger locations, and the number of chargers at the central terminal under variable ridership, dwell time, and travel times. In 2023, [Foda et al. \(2023\)](#) presented an integer linear optimization model that determined the location and capacity of charging infrastructure, battery capacity, and charging schedules, considering variable electricity prices, grid constraints, and trip-level energy consumption rates. [Wang et al. \(2023\)](#) focused on resolving charging conflicts between multiple bus lines, mitigating battery degradation from overcharging and over-discharging, and ensuring seamless charging continuity. They introduced two MILP models for en-route charging station location, battery sizing, and charging scheduling optimization. Finally, [McCabe and Ban \(2023\)](#) introduced a MILP model that uniquely incorporated deadheading costs in the objective function, determining the locations and quantity of chargers, as well as the location, duration, and sequence of charger visits for each bus. By explicitly considering charging duration as a variable, the authors provide a model that allows for partial recharge in the derived solutions.

In recently published studies, [Mortensen and Gunther \(2024\)](#) devised a method for deriving optimal charging plans given a specific number of fleets and charging station locations. They model the problem as a sequential decision problem, where information from problems initially solved in the sequence is passed on to the next. This approach to the problem is ultimately a heuristic one and is applicable to considerably large input datasets. Similarly, in another recent study, [Gkiotsalitis et al. \(2025\)](#) introduce an exact formulation to the integrated problem of CSLP and charging scheduling that can be solved for mid-sized bus networks.

2.3. The integrated planning problem of charging station location and charging scheduling, including energy grid considerations

Transitioning to electric bus fleets requires deploying charging infrastructure across various urban sites, each influenced by energy pricing and grid transmission or distribution constraints. This section reviews research on the CSLP and related sub-problems, with particular emphasis on the interaction between electric bus operations and energy grid dynamics.

Several studies have focused on integrating stochasticity into the CSLP and its interaction with the energy grid. For instance, [Liu et al. \(2018\)](#) addressed uncertainty in energy consumption by developing a robust optimization MILP model that specifies the number and type of fast chargers at each stop and the battery sizes of buses. Similarly, [An \(2020\)](#) created a stochastic integer program to optimize the placement of charging stations and the bus fleet size simultaneously, accounting for unpredictable variations in charging demands and Time-of-Use (ToU) electricity tariffs.

Beyond ToU tariffs, several research works have considered peak demand charges. [He et al. \(2019\)](#) introduced a MILP model designed to optimize the planning of fast-charging stations for an electric bus system. This model concurrently addresses the deployment of fast-charging stations, the installation of energy storage systems (ESSs), and the capacity of onboard batteries for battery electric buses (BEBs). A key feature of the proposed model is its inclusion of demand charges, a substantial component of bus operation costs that has been consistently overlooked in previous research.

In 2022, [Zhou et al. \(2022\)](#) tackled the integrated planning problem of deploying charging stations while considering the charging scheduling of electric buses. This study incorporated ToU tariffs, demand charges, and the optimization of electric bus battery capacity, focusing on the deployment of fast chargers. [Gairola and Nezamuddin \(2023\)](#) proposed an integrated optimization

framework for BEB infrastructure planning combined with charging scheduling. Their model accounts for required charging power and charger quantities while considering ToU electricity tariffs and demand charges.

Foda and Mohamed (2024) developed three optimization models to achieve the optimal configuration of BEB charging infrastructure (component sizing) and operation (charging schedule) in transit systems. Their models minimize the total cost of ownership of the BEB system and electricity costs based on ToU tariffs, and they also introduce a model to minimize well-to-wheel Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. In this, but also in previous works, Foda et al. (2023) consider partial and continuous charging and allow each bus to be charged up to different battery level during its recovery time (i.e. downtime). Liu et al. (2021) introduce an optimization model for electric bus charging infrastructure that accounts for power matching between chargers and batteries, as well as seasonal variations affecting battery performance. In another study by the same authors, Liu et al. (2023) address the issue of solar-powered bus charging infrastructure by incorporating Photovoltaic and Energy Storage Systems (PESS) to improve the resilience of public transport, particularly during charging service interruptions or when charging capacity is reduced due to service degradation. Wang et al. (2017) develop an optimization framework for electric bus recharging that simultaneously determines charging station locations, charger allocation, and recharging schedules, incorporating partial recharge strategies to enhance flexibility and cost efficiency. Applied to a real-world transit network in Davis, California, their model demonstrates how strategically placed fast-charging stations and optimized scheduling can eliminate range anxiety while minimizing total annual cost.

2.4. Contribution of this study

Several mathematical programming models have been proposed for the CSLP and its variations over the past few years. They vary across many dimensions of the problem, such as the objective function considered, the problem solution approach, the planning horizon, exact decisions to be optimized, and how constraints to the problem are expressed.

As can be seen in Table 1, several studies are closely connected to our research and have provided foundational insights. Starting with the work of An (2020), the current research aims to build upon their model by introducing disaggregate-level charging scheduling constraints. This addition allows the model to consider specific bus-to-time-slot assignments, guaranteeing no scheduling conflicts in charging plans.

Concerning Foda and Mohamed (2024), this research extends the scope to explore optimal charger locations that can be flexibly placed within urban environments. While Foda and Mohamed (2024) incorporate deadhead times as 'recovery time' per bus line, this model approaches the problem by setting stop coordinates as input parameters and considers deadhead times between each bus service's last stop and each potential charger location.

Similarly, the work by Gairola and Nezamuddin (2023) has contributed significantly by including ToU tariffs and peak demand considerations. Although their model focuses on multiple objectives without explicitly treating deadhead times, this study attempts to incorporate both deadhead times and bi-objective modeling to examine monetary costs and operational metrics (i.e. deadhead times). Also, the article by Wang et al. (2017) introduces an exact MILP model which accounts for important problem parameters, such as deadheading distance and ToU Tariffs, but does not consider multiple charger types or maximum demand charge.

The studies by Liu et al. (2021, 2023) have greatly influenced the direction of this work. These studies incorporate disaggregate charging scheduling constraints, and their latest study (Liu et al., 2023) includes ToU tariffs. Our research builds on their approach by explicitly considering specific charger types, deadhead times, and peak demand charges. In more detail, a differentiation point to the works by Liu et al. (2021, 2023) is methodological since our work employs a bi-objective model to examine the trade-off between monetary cost and deadhead times in its analysis. This methodological difference is evident across all the articles reviewed. Among them, only the study by He et al. (2023) addresses a bi-objective MILP formulation and computes the Pareto front for the problem solved in that study. However, it overlooks several problem dimensions relevant in the current context, such as the charging scheduling sub-problem.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, up to now, no study has provided an exact approach to extending electric bus charging networks, especially when considering previous advancements of the literature on the CSLP. While Wang et al. (2021) and Zhang et al. (2021) address this problem, they do not strictly build on the Electric Bus CSLP literature. Wang et al. propose a pricing-aware real-time charging scheduling system using a Markov Decision Process (MDP) to optimize charging costs based on electricity price variations, validated with real-world data from Shenzhen. Zhang et al. develop a framework for locating and expanding charging stations using gridded Affinity Propagation (AP) clustering and a sequential expansion rule, considering factors like land cost, traffic, power grid capacity, and demand growth to support long-term network planning.

Summarizing, the contribution of this study to the state-of-the-art is:

1. The development of an exact analytical bi-objective mathematical model for extending an already existing network of charging stations considering the charging scheduling of electric buses and the energy pricing, including Time-of-Use (ToU) Tariffs, Peak Demand Charge and Partial Recharging scenarios.
2. The inclusion of different charger types, and their explicit consideration in the problem's formulation and the constraints for charger placement, bus charging scheduling as well as the consumption of electric energy according to two charger power output levels (slow and fast).
3. The application of the ϵ -constraint method on the exact bi-objective mathematical model for the calculation of Pareto optimal solution in regard to the two objectives of the monetary cost for installation and operating the network of charging stations, as well as the deadhead times of electric buses for charging purposes.
4. The application of the methodological framework to real-world networks (New York and Limassol), demonstrating the trade-offs between monetary costs related to the installation and utilization of charging infrastructure and the vehicle running costs.

Table 1
Literature review summary.

Reference	Objective	Solution Approach	Charger Location	Multiple Charger Types	Disaggregate Charging Scheduling Constraints	Deadheading Time or Distance	ToU Tariffs	Demand Charges	Partial Recharge	CS Network Extension
He et al. (2023)	Electrified Transit Miles, Monetary Cost	Bi-objective MILP, normalized normal constraint method	✓	✓						
Gkiotsalitis et al. (2025)	Deadhead times	MILP	✓	✓	✓					
Foda et al. (2023)	Monetary Cost, Grid Impact, Emissions	Surrogate Model	✓	✓	✓		✓			
Wang et al. (2023)	Charging Facility Cost, Battery Cost, Charging Cost	MILP	✓		✓		✓			
McCabe and Ban (2023)	Monetary Cost	Heuristic	✓		✓	✓				
An (2020)	Monetary Cost, Deadheading	Stochastic IP, Lagrangian Relaxation	✓	✓		✓	✓			
He et al. (2019)	Monetary Cost, quantity of equipment deployed	MILP	✓	✓			✓	✓		
Zhou et al. (2022)	Battery Size, Number of Chargers	MILP	(Specific Terminals)		✓		✓	✓		
Gairola and Nezamuddin (2023)	Monetary Cost, Battery Size	MILP	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		
Foda and Mohamed (2024)	Monetary Cost, GHG Emissions	MILP		✓	✓	✓	✓			
Liu et al. (2021)	Monetary Cost, Waiting Time	Surrogate Model	✓		✓		(single tariff value)			
Liu et al. (2023)	Monetary Cost, Service Robustness	Two-Stage Exact Approach	✓		✓		✓			
Wang et al. (2017)	Deadhead Time, Monetary cost	MILP	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	
Wang et al. (2021)	Monetary cost	Heuristic	(existing locations)		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Zhang et al. (2021)	Monetary cost	Multi-stage heuristic	✓							✓
This Study	Deadhead Time, Monetary Cost	Bi-objective MILP, ϵ -constraint Method	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

3. Methodology

The methodology for the research work described in this article is given in three subsections, with the first presenting the definition of the problem, the second presenting the bi-objective MILP formulation of the problem, and the third subsection discussing the ϵ -constraint method used for finding Pareto optimal solutions for our mathematical formulation.

3.1. Problem statement

In response to the identified needs and respective research directions, we attempt to enhance the definition and formulation of the integrated problem of the Charging Station Location Selection when considering charging scheduling and energy consumption considerations. As compared to previous reports, this addition to the problem includes two distinct topics: Firstly, we seek optimal extensions of the charging stations network, which entails identifying the most suitable locations for charger installations of two types (slow and fast), taking into account an existing initial placement of chargers established before our planning efforts. Secondly, we co-analyze the problem's two key objectives, including the monetary cost and deadhead times that emerge from covering the charging demand of a fleet of electric buses during their daily operation.

Based on these topics, we present the following definition for the problem attempted to be solved in this article:

“Given initial sets of pre-existing slow and fast charging stations located at various sites \mathcal{V} , along with a specified Time-of-Use tariff structure, peak demand charges, and a maximum available budget \mathcal{B} , determine the optimal placement of new slow and fast charging stations. The objective is to meet the charging demand of an electric bus fleet while minimizing installation costs, daily charging expenses, and deadhead time across a set of designated bus trips \mathcal{K} .”

For this integrated problem, several planning horizons are considered. The placement of charging stations is a strategic planning problem, combined with the charging scheduling problem, for which a tactical planning horizon is assumed. Furthermore, the problem is influenced by the potentially conflicting objectives of the public transport operator, a key stakeholder in planning the charging station network extension process. In this context, two distinct objectives are considered for the bus fleet operator:

1. *Objective 1:* The minimization of deadhead time, which is the travel time between the last stop of the bus line (end of itinerary) and the arrival time at the charging station location.
2. *Objective 2:* The minimization of the monetary cost of installing new chargers and the minimization of the daily operational charging costs stemming from the quantity of energy consumed according to the Time of Use Tariffs and demand charge cost (based on peak demand).

These objectives are not always aligned. In many cases, they can be contradictory since installing more chargers near the end locations of bus trips can substantially reduce deadhead times, but at the same time, it can increase installation and maintenance costs. Regarding the mathematical formulation of such a problem, one may expect that solutions that are optimal for one of the two objectives may not necessarily be optimal for the other. For that reason, our problem is formulated as a bi-objective optimization problem considering the following assumptions:

1. A vital aspect of our planning is having day-ahead knowledge of a specified set of trips and the buses assigned to them, which will require charging at some point during the day. Represented as set \mathcal{K} , this group includes trips where buses, after completing their service at the final stop of their assigned route, must undergo recharging at predetermined times throughout the day.
2. Concerning the charging schedule, lines are not confined to designated charging locations or clusters of locations. Consequently, a bus line may be allocated to any candidate charging station in the urban area as required.
3. The model assumes a daily charging horizon with a cyclic structure across consecutive days. Specifically, the primary charging period is scheduled from 6:00 to 24:00, during which regular bus charging operations occur. In addition, a corrective charging window is available from the end of daily operations (at 24:00) until the start of the operations of the following day (at 6:00), allowing for corrective charging during nighttime if deviations from the planned charging are detected.
4. Each charger type has a predefined charging time slot duration and number of slots per day based on its electrical power supply.
5. If a bus trip is assigned to a charging slot, then this time slot is entirely allocated to the vehicle, irrespective of the actual charging duration required. Thus, the corresponding charger remains occupied for the full length of the time slot, even if the bus completes charging before the slot's conclusion.
6. When a bus is assigned to either a slow or fast charger, three possible charging scenarios may arise. In the first scenario, the bus charges to its full battery capacity. In the second scenario, the available charging power and slot duration are insufficient for a full charge, so the bus charges according to the maximum energy that can be provided by the charger during the charging slot. In the third scenario, although the bus could reach full capacity within the allotted time, it undergoes only a partial recharge due to a limited number of remaining trips for the day.
7. Based on the three charging scenarios, the charging time for a given trip in set \mathcal{K} is not constant for all trips. It depends on the electric vehicle's total battery capacity, remaining battery level at the end of the trip, and the type of charger employed (slow or fast).

Based on these assumptions, the mathematical notation for the modeling of the problem is provided in the next Section 3.2.

Fig. 1. Representation of the three time horizons (F_1 , F_2 , and F_3) considered as sets in the problem formulation, along with the associated parameters $z_{f_3}^s$ and $z_{f_3}^h$.

3.2. Problem formulation

In the current formulation, we consider a set of bus lines \mathcal{L} which perform a set of \mathcal{M} bus trips, out of which a subset \mathcal{K} requires charging ($\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$). These \mathcal{K} vehicle trips must be assigned to a set of available charging stations \mathcal{N} and scheduled to respective time slots \mathcal{F} . We consider that several chargers of two types, slow and fast, can be installed in a pre-defined set of candidate charging station locations \mathcal{V} . Several potential charger installation options \mathcal{N} (i.e. chargers), may be available at a single physical location. The set \mathcal{N} of potential charger installations expands to the set of available charging slots \mathcal{F} .

Given these considerations, our objective is to allocate $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ vehicle trips requiring charging to the available chargers \mathcal{N} and charging slots \mathcal{F} in a manner that minimizes financial upfront investments and operational costs, as well as vehicle deadhead times for charging purposes. The set of potential charger installations \mathcal{N} can be divided into the set of slow chargers \mathcal{N}_1 and the set of fast chargers \mathcal{N}_2 . Within these, the set \mathcal{N}_3 denotes the already installed slow chargers at any location within \mathcal{V} , while \mathcal{N}_5 represents the potentially new slow charging stations. Similarly, the set \mathcal{N}_4 corresponds to the already installed fast charging stations, and \mathcal{N}_6 represents the new potential fast charging stations. Given these, it is noteworthy to mention that $\mathcal{N}_1 = \mathcal{N}_3 \cup \mathcal{N}_5$ and $\mathcal{N}_2 = \mathcal{N}_4 \cup \mathcal{N}_6$.

Additionally, in this formulation, we assume three-time horizons. One is used for the time slots of the slow chargers, one for the time slots of the fast chargers, and one for demand charge time periods, as defined by an energy management authority or an energy grid operator. Each slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ can be utilized multiple times throughout the day, resulting in a set of charging time slots \mathcal{F}_1 (i.e. first time horizon). Similarly, each fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ results in a set of charging time slots \mathcal{F}_2 (i.e. second time horizon). Set \mathcal{F}_3 is used for the third time horizon, indicating the demand charge time periods, which are considered the time windows based on which the grid operator calculates its charges.

The relationship between charging time slots \mathcal{F}_1 , \mathcal{F}_2 , and the demand charge time periods \mathcal{F}_3 , is an integral part of the modeling presented in this article. In this context, we use superscripts s to denote parameters and variables specific to slow chargers and h for those related to fast chargers. This naming convention helps to clearly distinguish between the two types of chargers but is not strictly necessary for the mathematical modeling itself. In addition to that, we consider the set $z_{f_3}^s$ mapping demand charge time periods f_3 to the time slots f_1 of slow chargers, such that $z_{f_3}^s \in \mathcal{F}_1$, when f_3 belongs to charging slot f_1 . Similarly, a set $z_{f_3}^h$ is introduced to map f_3 to the fast charger time slots f_2 , where $z_{f_3}^h \in \mathcal{F}_2$ when f_3 belongs to f_2 . In Fig. 1, an example is illustrated of an 8-h period for the three time horizons \mathcal{F}_1 , \mathcal{F}_2 and \mathcal{F}_3 , as well as the parameters $z_{f_3}^s$ and $z_{f_3}^h$ that are used for their association.

To further include time representation in our model, we define df_1 , df_2 , and df_3 as the duration of each time period f_1 , f_2 , and f_3 . Their relationship, which will be presented in greater detail in the rest of Section 3, is given by $r^s = \frac{df_1}{df_3}$ and $r^h = \frac{df_2}{df_3}$. At last, since df_1 , df_2 and df_3 are considered to be measured in minutes, hr_1 , hr_2 and hr_3 are the same quantities in hours. The start times for charging slots at slow and fast charging stations are given by $c_{f_1}^s$ and $c_{f_2}^s$, respectively. Depending on the state of charge when trip k requires charging, the latest allowable start time for charging at a slow charger is p_k^s , and for a fast charger, is p_k^h .

In modeling electric bus vehicles, key parameters are considered such as battery capacity (minimum and maximum state of charge), driving range, and the state of charge at charging times. Specifically, the State of Charge (SoC) for each trip k , denoted as SOC_k , represents the energy level in the battery when the electric bus completes its operations and arrives at the last stop of the bus line, where charging is required. The minimum allowable state of charge for each trip is denoted by SOC_k^{\min} , and the maximum state of charge (i.e. bus battery capacity) is denoted by SOC_k^{\max} . Additionally, we consider the charging power of slow and fast chargers, represented by CP^s and CP^h , respectively. Parameters DCP^s and DCP^h represent the power of the two types of chargers reduced to the duration of f_3 , which is df_3 .

The time at which trip k concludes (reaches its final stop) and must proceed to a charging station is represented by τ_k . The deadhead travel time t_{kj} is the travel time between the final stop of trip k and a potential charger location j , forming a $|\mathcal{K}| \times |\mathcal{N}|$ matrix. The arrival time τ_k , when considered together with the estimated deadhead time t_{kj} , enables us to formulate the charging scheduling constraints presented in later sections. The parameter e denotes the battery consumption per unit distance traveled. Given this first presentation of the problem's nomenclature, below, we provide the decision variables of the formulation:

- $x_j \in \{0, 1\}$, where $x_j = 1$ if we decide to install charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$, and 0 otherwise. Notably, $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N}_1 \cup \mathcal{N}_2 = \mathcal{N}_3 \cup \mathcal{N}_4 \cup \mathcal{N}_5 \cup \mathcal{N}_6$, indicating simultaneous selection of the charging location and type.
- $q_{kj} \in \{0, 1\}$, where $q_{kj} = 1$ if trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is assigned to charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$, and 0 otherwise.
- $u_{kjj_1}^s \in \{0, 1\}$, where $u_{kjj_1}^s = 1$ if trip k starts charging at time slot $f_1 \in F_1$ at a slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$.
- $u_{kjj_2}^h \in \{0, 1\}$, where $u_{kjj_2}^h = 1$ if trip k starts charging at time slot $f_2 \in F_2$ at a fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$.

Furthermore, several additional dependent variables are considered regarding the charging scheduling of the electric buses in the third time horizon F_3 , as well as the deadhead time that emerges from the scheduling assignments:

- $UD_{jff_3}^s \in \{0, 1\}$, where $UD_{jff_3}^s = 1$, if any trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is charging at a slow charger $j \in N1$ demand charge time period $f_3 \in F_3$.
- $UD_{jff_3}^h \in \{0, 1\}$, where $UD_{jff_3}^h = 1$, if any trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is charging at a fast charger $j \in N2$ demand charge time period $f_3 \in F_3$.
- $y_k \in \mathbb{R}^+$, representing the deadheading time of each trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$.

The formulation necessitates the definition of the following additional dependent variables to accurately quantify the amount of energy transferred from the charging station network, and by extension, the energy grid, to the electric buses during the charging phase:

- $EC_{kjj_1}^s \in \mathbb{R}^+$, representing the amount of energy transferred from a slow charger $j \in N_1$ to the bus of trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at time slot $f_1 \in F_1$.
- $EC_{kjj_2}^h \in \mathbb{R}^+$, representing the amount of energy transferred from a fast charger $j \in N_2$ to the bus of trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ demand charge time period $f_2 \in F_2$.
- $DC_{kjj_3}^s \in \mathbb{R}^+$, representing the amount of energy transferred from a slow charger $j \in N_1$ to the bus of trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ demand charge time period $f_3 \in F_3$.
- $DC_{kjj_3}^h \in \mathbb{R}^+$, representing the amount of energy transferred from a fast charger $j \in N_2$ to the bus of trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ demand charge time period $f_3 \in F_3$.
- $DEC_{f_3} \in \mathbb{R}^+$, representing the energy consumption at all chargers, slow and fast, during each charging time slot $f_3 \in F_3$.
- $IP^{\max} \in \mathbb{N}^+$, representing the maximum power consumed across all demand charge time periods $f_3 \in F_3$.

To calculate the monetary costs (aggregate quantities), such as the peak Demand Charge Costs (DCC) and the Charging Stations Installation Costs (CSI), we are required to define some parameters that represent energy pricing. Such a parameter is T_{f_3} , which represents the Time of Use Tariffs, which is the price per kilowatt-hours (kWh) at a specific charging time slot $f_3 \in F_3$. The Demand Charge Rate DCR , expressed in monetary units, is the financial cost applied to the demand charge period with the peak power usage across all periods f_3 denoted by IP^{\max} and measured in kilowatts (kW). The fixed cost of installing a charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$ is represented by b_j . The total budget allocated for installing charging stations is minimized as part of the first objective of the formulation but also has to remain under a specific total budget b^{\max} .

Given these parameters, the aggregate variables for monetary costs that concern the extension and operation of the CS network are the following:

$$TOUC = \sum_{f_3}^{F_3} (T_{f_3} \cdot DEC_{f_3}) \tag{1}$$

$$DCC = DCR \cdot IP^{\max} \tag{2}$$

$$CSI = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_3 \cup \mathcal{N}_6} x_j b_j \tag{3}$$

Mathematical expression (1) gives the Time-of-Use Costs (TOUC), which is the energy consumption costs according to the ToU tariffs T_{f_3} for the buses' recharging sessions at slow and fast chargers. Mathematical expression (2) gives the formula for the calculation of demand charge cost DCC , while relationship (3) provides the Charging Station Installation (CSI) cost calculation for the new chargers to be installed as part of the CS network extension. Given this discussion, the nomenclature of this formulation is summarized in the appendix Table A.1.

3.2.1. Objective functions

To address the two objectives of the problem under investigation, this formulation incorporates two objective functions that are not always aligned and can have a contradictory effect for the electric bus fleet operator. The first objective function minimizes deadhead time for each electric bus requiring charging from set \mathcal{K} , which is defined as the deadhead travel time between the last stop of each bus line, where the trip is completed, and the location of the designated charger. Consequently, the first objective of the problem is articulated as follows in Eq. (4):

$$\text{minimize } \mathcal{O}_1 = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} y_k = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} t_{kj} q_{kj} \text{ for all } k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (4)$$

The second objective function represents the monetary cost associated with the operation of the bus fleet. This includes both the initial capital investments required for the installation of new charging stations and the expansion of the existing network, as well as the potential operational costs associated with charging the electric vehicles for their daily use. These cost components are integrated into the second objective of the problem, as delineated by Eq. (5):

$$\text{minimize } \mathcal{O}_2 = TOUC + DCC + CSI \quad (5)$$

3.2.2. Modeling of the CS network extension problem

To model the CS network extension problem as an extension of the CSLP, it is necessary to formulate several constraints as follows:

$$x_j = 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_3 \cup \mathcal{N}_4 \quad (6)$$

$$q_{kj} \leq x_j \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} q_{kj} \geq x_j \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} q_{kj} = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_j b_j \leq b^{\max} \quad (10)$$

Constraint (6) guarantees that the binary variable x_j takes the value of one for already installed chargers of both types depending on the set that they belong to \mathcal{N}_3 and \mathcal{N}_4 . Constraint (7) connects the values of q_{kj} and x_j for our mathematical program, allowing an assignment of bus k to a charger j only if a charger is established, given the value of x_j . Constraint (8) guarantees that if x_j equals 1, then at least one bus k is assigned to the charger at j , while Constraint (9) makes sure that all buses that need charging get assigned to at least one charger j . At last, while two types of charging stations are considered, the installation of new chargers of either type does not only affect the overall solution of the formulation through \mathcal{O}_2 but has to remain under the total budget of b^{\max} , as also indicated by Eq. (10).

3.2.3. Constraints of the charging scheduling sub-problem

To integrate the charging scheduling sub-problem into our MILP formulation, we present below a series of constraints that are mainly used to connect the binary decision variables $u_{kjf_1}^s$ and $u_{kjf_2}^h$ with the rest of the sub-problems.

$$\sum_{f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1} u_{kjf_1}^s + \sum_{f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2} u_{kjf_2}^h \leq q_{kj} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_1} u_{kjf_1}^s + \sum_{f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_2} u_{kjf_2}^h = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} u_{kjf_1}^s \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1 \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} u_{kjf_2}^h \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2 \quad (14)$$

$$(1 - u_{kjf_1}^s)M + u_{kjf_1}^s c_{f_1}^s \geq (\tau_k + t_{kj}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1 \quad (15)$$

$$(1 - u_{kjf_2}^h)M + u_{kjf_2}^h c_{f_2}^h \geq (\tau_k + t_{kj}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2 \quad (16)$$

$$-(1 - u_{kjf_1}^s)M + u_{kjf_1}^s c_{f_1}^s \leq (p_k^s + t_{kj}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1 \quad (17)$$

$$-(1 - u_{kjf_2}^h)M + u_{kjf_2}^h c_{f_2}^h \leq (p_k^h + t_{kj}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2 \quad (18)$$

Constraint (11) guarantees that if an assigned of bus k to charger j , then depending on whether j is a fast or slow charger, at maximum one of $u_{kjf_1}^s$ and $u_{kjf_2}^h$ variables takes the value of 1 for either one of the charging time slots f_1 or f_2 . Constraint (12) works with (11), enforcing that each bus k gets scheduled to exactly one charging time slot, either that is f_1 or f_2 . Constraint (13) and (14) ensure that for each charging time slot, each slow and fast charger (belonging to either \mathcal{N}_1 or \mathcal{N}_2) gets a maximum of 1 bus assigned to them. Please note that these constraints do not limit the different bus trips k that need charging to attend different time slots f_1 or f_2 of the same location throughout the day. Constraints (15) and (16) guarantee the time continuity in

our formulation by re-assuring that the start of charging slots $c_{f_1}^s$ and $c_{f_2}^h$ is later the arrival times of buses to the locations of the chargers (i.e. $\tau_k + t_{kj}$). Given that the bus is assumed to need to return to the daily operation of services or return to a depot, we make sure that the charging of each bus starts within a time window (i.e. p^s and p^h), with constraints (17) and (18), that guarantee that the buses start charging within a reasonable time-frame after they reach the charger location.

3.2.4. Energy consumption modeling according to three charging scenarios

This research presents a MILP formulation that incorporates three distinct charging scenarios encountered during the allocation of buses to charging stations for recharging.

- In the first charging scenario, the bus charges throughout the entire duration of the charging slot (f_1 or f_2) but does not reach its maximum battery capacity SOC_k^{\max} . This occurs because the charger's power output during the specified charging slot duration (f_1 or f_2) is insufficient to fully charge the battery before the slot concludes.
- In the second charging scenario, the bus does not charge for the entire duration of the charging slot, as its maximum state of charge SOC_k^{\max} is reached before the slot ends. This occurs because the power supplied by the slow or fast charger during its respective time slot (f_1 or f_2) exceeds the remaining battery capacity of bus k to be charged, taking into account the state of charge SOC_k at the last stop of the bus trip, the energy consumption e , and the distance traveled to the charger d_{kj} .
- Additionally, a third scenario is introduced, which accounts for the case when the bus should recharge partially, charging up to a percentage of its battery capacity. This percentage is determined based on a partial recharge strategy employed by the public transport services operator, primarily considering the energy required to execute the remaining trips scheduled for the bus line on that day.

The main goal of the formulation is to choose whether a bus line $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges at one of the locations $j \in \mathcal{N}$ and, if yes, which respective slots (f_1 or f_2) will be used. Given that the SOC_k at all bus lines' last stops is provided, as well as the travel distances to all existing or potentially new locations for electric chargers, these data can be combined through a pre-calculation process to calculate energy quantities that will be potentially transferred to electric buses based on the calculated solutions by our MILP model.

Given this concept, the precalculation process includes two steps. In the first step, we utilize parameters $CC_{kjf_1}^s$ and $CC_{kjf_2}^h$ for slow and fast chargers respectively, which take binary values and define whether an assignment of a bus k to a charger j follows the first or second charging scenario. In more detail, the following parameters are pre-calculated for all possible combinations of bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ attending any charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$ during time slots f_1 or f_2 :

- The $EC_{kj}^{\max} = SOC_k^{\max} - SOC_k + e \cdot d_{kj} = \text{energy (kWh)}$ that can be transferred from a charger j to the bus k during any time slot, if the bus k charges at charger j .
- $SME^s = hr_1 \cdot CP^s$, which is the maximum energy (in kWh) that can be transferred from a *slow charger* to the bus during a slow charger time slot f_1 .
- $SME^h = hr_2 \cdot CP^h$, which is the maximum energy (in kWh) that can be transferred from a *fast charger* to the bus during a fast charger time slot f_2 .
- CC_{kj}^s , which is a matrix of parameters, which take the value of 1 if the bus serving trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges for the whole duration of any charging slot f_1 at charging outlet $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ ($SOC_k - e \cdot d_{kj} + SME^s < SOC_k^{\max}$). The parameter takes the value of 0 if the bus charges up to its full battery capacity ($SOC_k - e \cdot d_{kj} + SME^s \geq SOC_k^{\max}$).
- CC_{kj}^h , which is a matrix of parameters, which take the value of 1 if the bus serving trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges for the whole duration of any charging slot f_2 at charging outlet $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ ($SOC_k - e \cdot d_{kj} + SME^h < SOC_k^{\max}$). The parameter takes the value of 0 if the bus charges up to its full battery capacity ($SOC_k - e \cdot d_{kj} + SME^h \geq SOC_k^{\max}$).
- $PEC_{kj}^s = SME^s \cdot CC_{kj}^s + EC_{kj}^{\max} \cdot (1 - CC_{kj}^s)$, represents the pre-calculated parameters for the amount of energy that can potentially be transferred from slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ to bus k , if bus k , given its SOC_k at the last stop of the bus line, the battery capacity of the vehicle SOC_k^{\max} and the minimum travel distance d_{kj} , is assigned to the slow charger j .
- $PEC_{kj}^h = SME^h \cdot CC_{kj}^h + EC_{kj}^{\max} \cdot (1 - CC_{kj}^h)$, similar to the previously mentioned pre-calculated parameter, PEC_{kj}^h represents the amount of energy that can potentially be transferred from fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ to bus k , if bus k , given its SOC_k at the last stop of the bus line, the battery capacity of the vehicle SOC_k^{\max} , and the minimum travel distance d_{kj} , is assigned to the fast charger j .

Then, in the second step of the precalculation process, we further examine whether the electric bus should charge up to PEC_{kj}^s or PEC_{kj}^h , which is the maximum energy that it can consume from the grid according to the first or second charging scenario, or if it should recharge for a part of the amount of that energy (i.e. third charging scenario). To achieve this goal, we introduce a piecewise linear function PR that depends on parameters SOC_k , SOC_k^{\max} , PEC_{kj}^s , PEC_{kj}^h as defined above, and five additional parameters ER , ER_{low} , ER_{high} , P_1 and P_2 . These five parameters define the partial recharge strategy of the public transport services operator with ER defining the required energy demand (kWh) for the bus to serve the remaining trips for the day, and ER_{low} and ER_{high} setting thresholds for what be considered as low or high remaining energy demand for each day. While ER can be calculated based on the number of remaining trips for the bus and the required energy to execute each trip, ER_{low} and ER_{high} are considered as specific percentages of SOC_k^{\max} .

At this stage, it is worth noting that the piecewise linear function can be adapted to suit a specific implementation of the model. It is also possible to extend it by incorporating additional branches or refining existing ones (e.g. adding more conditional statements),

thereby enabling the representation of more complex partial recharge strategies tailored to the operational requirements of specific electric bus fleet operators. Furthermore, an alternative approach could involve using the number of remaining trips per bus rather than the specific energy demand, as proposed next.

Based on this context, parameters P_1 and P_2 are utilized to specify the state of charge as percentages of SOC_k^{\max} under different trip conditions. With these parameters now defined, the function PR is presented next, applicable to both PEC_{kj}^s and PEC_{kj}^h :

$$PR(PEC) = \begin{cases} PEC & \text{if } ER > ER_{high}, \\ P_1 \cdot SOC_k^{\max} & \text{if } ER_{low} < ER \leq ER_{high} \text{ and } \frac{SoC_k + PEC}{SOC_k^{\max}} \geq P_1, \\ P_2 \cdot SOC_k^{\max} & \text{if } ER \leq ER_{low} \text{ and } \frac{SoC_k + PEC}{SOC_k^{\max}} \geq P_2, \\ PEC & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

where $PEC \in \{PEC_{kj}^s, PEC_{kj}^h\}$.

Given the aforementioned parameters and the pre-calculated values for the electric bus network and the area of application, \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s and \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h can be used in the MILP formulation to guarantee that the electric bus line is charged according to the real-world settings.

- $\widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s = PR(PEC_{kj}^s)$ = The final amount of energy that is pre-calculated for the case that the bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ attending any slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ during time slots $f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1$.
- $\widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h = PR(PEC_{kj}^h)$ = The final amount of energy that is pre-calculated for the case that the bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ attending any fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ during time slots $f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2$.

3.2.5. Time-of-use tariffs modeling

ToU Tariffs are a dynamic pricing model where electricity rates vary according to the time of day, aligning with demand and supply fluctuations. For bus line operators with substantial electricity demand, a B2B contract with the energy grid operator or an energy management authority usually defines these electricity costs during off-peak hours and higher costs during peak periods. This pricing scheme usually incentivizes operators to charge buses during off-peak times, thereby reducing operational costs. In collaboration with Peak demand charges, they aim to ease grid demand during peak hours.

In our MILP model, ToU Tariffs are included by calculating the monetary cost of using energy throughout the different times of the day. As discussed, the amount of energy for every potential assignment of bus k to charger j is pre-calculated with quantities \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s and \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h . Based on this, the calculation of $EC_{kjjf_1}^s$ and $EC_{kjjf_2}^h$ for the actual amount of energy consumed based on charging scheduling assignments $u_{kjjf_1}^s$ and $u_{kjjf_2}^h$ is given below:

$$EC_{kjjf_1}^s \leq M \cdot u_{kjjf_1}^s \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1 \quad (19)$$

$$EC_{kjjf_2}^h \leq M \cdot u_{kjjf_2}^h \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2 \quad (20)$$

$$EC_{kjjf_1}^s \geq (-M) \cdot (1 - u_{kjjf_1}^s) + \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1 \quad (21)$$

$$EC_{kjjf_1}^s \leq M \cdot (1 - u_{kjjf_1}^s) + \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_1 \in \mathcal{F}_1 \quad (22)$$

$$EC_{kjjf_2}^h \geq (-M) \cdot (1 - u_{kjjf_2}^h) + \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2 \quad (23)$$

$$EC_{kjjf_2}^h \leq M \cdot (1 - u_{kjjf_2}^h) + \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_2 \in \mathcal{F}_2 \quad (24)$$

Constraints (19) and (20) guarantee that $EC_{kjjf_1}^s$ and $EC_{kjjf_2}^h$ take the value of 0, if the respective assignments, as defined by $u_{kjjf_1}^s$ and $u_{kjjf_2}^h$ are also 0. Constraints (21) and (22) assure that if the assignment from k to the slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$, at charging time slot f_1 takes place, then $EC_{kjjf_1}^s$ takes the necessary pre-calculated \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s . Similarly, (23) and (24) guarantee the same for the assignments of buses to fast charger and respective time slots.

In order to calculate the exact energy consumed per billable time period f_3 , we need to calculate energy consumption at a higher granularity level. With respect to the three pre-calculated scenarios, dependent variables $DC_{kjjf_3}^s$ (slow chargers) and $DC_{kjjf_3}^h$ (fast chargers) need to take values according to values $EC_{kjjf_1}^s$ and $EC_{kjjf_2}^h$. To achieve that, we need to further pre-calculate the energy quantities transferred for each demand charge period f_3 given the energy transferred in respective charging time slots f_1 and f_2 . For that reason, the following quantities are introduced:

- $DCP^s = \frac{hr_1 \cdot CP^s}{r^s} = hr_3 \cdot CP^s$, which corresponds to the maximum amount of energy per demand charge period f_3 for slow chargers,
- $DCP^h = \frac{hr_2 \cdot CP^h}{r^h} = hr_3 \cdot CP^h$, which corresponds to the maximum amount of energy per demand charge period f_3 for fast chargers,
- $FCS_{kj}^s = \left\lfloor \frac{\widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s}{DCP^s} \right\rfloor$, which corresponds to the number of time periods f_3 within any respective charging time slot f_1 that consume energy equal to DCP^s , out of the total number of r^s slots within any f_1 that is chosen for the charging of k at j ,

Fig. 2. Illustration of F_1 and F_3 for an 8-h hypothetical time horizon where a bus k is selected to charge at $f_1 = 2$ of F_1 and respective slots of F_3 , where $f_3 \in \{9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16\}$.

- $FCS_{kj}^h = \left\lceil \frac{\widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h}{DCP^h} \right\rceil$, which corresponds to the number of time periods f_3 within any respective charging time slot f_2 that consume energy equal to DCP^h , out of the total number of r^h slots within any f_2 that is chosen for the charging of k at j ,
- $RE_{kj}^s = \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s - FCS_{kj}^s \cdot DCP^s$, which is the amount of energy transferred from a charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ to a bus k during the time period $f_3 = FCS_{kj}^s + 1$,
- $RE_{kj}^h = \widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h - FCS_{kj}^h \cdot DCP^h$, which is the amount of energy transferred from a charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ to a bus k during the time period $f_3 = FCS_{kj}^h + 1$,

Given these pre-calculated values, with Constraints (25) and (26) guarantee that DC^s_{k,j,f_3} and DC^h_{k,j,f_3} take value of zero, when respective dependent variables $EC^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}}$ and $EC^h_{k,j,z^h_{f_3}}$ are also zero.

$$DC^s_{k,j,f_3} \leq M \cdot EC^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_3 \in F_3 \quad (25)$$

$$DC^h_{k,j,f_3} \leq M \cdot EC^h_{k,j,z^h_{f_3}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_3 \in F_3 \quad (26)$$

When $EC^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}}$ and $EC^h_{k,j,z^h_{f_3}}$ are nonzero, their values should be mapped to DC^s_{k,j,f_3} and DC^h_{k,j,f_3} , depending on whether the bus charges during the full f_1 or f_2 slots. To reduce the number of variables and constraints, and thereby the complexity of the model, this formulation focuses solely on the energy consumed from the grid without explicitly accounting for the time duration of charging in a variable of the model. In that regard, two cases of energy transfer can be considered regarding the amount of energy transferred by the energy grid to the bus and the relationship of time horizons F_1 , F_2 and F_3 . The first case of energy transfer applies to the first charging scenario, where the electric bus charges for the full duration of the charging slot (whether that is f_1 or f_2 , along with the associated f_3 slots). This case is illustrated in Fig. 2, which depicts an example with time horizons F_1 and F_3 and the case when a full $f_1 = 2$ slot of F_1 is selected for charging.

Alternatively, a second case arises under charging scenarios two and three, where the bus does not charge for the entire duration of an f_1 or f_2 slot, and the associated slots of F_3 . In this case, while some of the f_3 slots will charge to full capacity, the final slot will only charge up to a specific amount of energy, denoted as RE^s_{kj} or RE^h_{kj} . In Fig. 3, an example is presented for this case, where a bus k is selected to charge for a fraction of $f_1 = 2$ of F_1 . With regards to the slots of F_3 , the bus fully charges for $f_3 \in \{9, 10, 11, 12, 13\}$, and charges partly for $f_3 = 14$ of F_3 , while respective variables DC^s_{k,j,f_3} for slots $f_3 = 15$ and $f_3 = 16$ of F_3 take the value of zero. For both Figs. 2 and 3, an 8-h horizon is hypothesized, which for the application of the model would be required to be extended to a daily horizon of 24 or 30 h.

Based on this discussion of three charging scenarios and two energy transfer cases, constraints (27) to (34) are introduced, based on which variables DC^s_{k,j,f_3} and DC^h_{k,j,f_3} take the necessary values:

$$DC^s_{k,j,f_3} \geq (-M) \cdot u^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} + DCP^s \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_3 \in F_3 : f_3 \leq FCS_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} \quad (27)$$

$$DC^s_{k,j,f_3} \leq DCP^s + M \cdot u^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_3 \in F_3 : f_3 \leq FCS_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} \quad (28)$$

$$DC^s_{k,j,f_3} \geq (-M) \cdot u^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} + RE^s_{kj} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_3 \in F_3 : f_3 = FCS_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} + 1 \quad (29)$$

$$DC^s_{k,j,f_3} \leq RE^s_{kj} + M \cdot u^s_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_3 \in F_3 : f_3 = FCS_{k,j,z^s_{f_3}} + 1 \quad (30)$$

$$DC^h_{k,j,f_3} \geq (-M) \cdot u^h_{k,j,z^h_{f_3}} + DCP^h \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_3 \in F_3 : f_3 \leq FCS_{k,j,z^h_{f_3}} \quad (31)$$

Fig. 3. Illustration of F_1 and F_3 for an 8-h hypothetical time horizon where a bus k is selected to charge for a fraction of $f_1 = 2$ of F_1 and respective slots of F_3 , where $f_3 \in [9, 10, 11, 12, 13]$ and partly for $f_3 = 14$.

$$DC^h_{k_j f_3} \leq DCP^h + M \cdot u^h_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 : f_3 \leq FCS_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} \quad (32)$$

$$DC^h_{k_j f_3} \geq (-M) \cdot u^h_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} + RE^h_{k_j} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 : f_3 = FCS_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} + 1 \quad (33)$$

$$DC^h_{k_j f_3} \leq RE^h_{k_j} + M \cdot u^h_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 : f_3 = FCS_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} + 1 \quad (34)$$

Constraints (27) to (34) apply to selected f_3 slots based on the values of the pre-calculated $FCS^s_{k_j}$ for slow chargers and $FCS^h_{k_j}$ for fast chargers. More specifically, constraints (27) and (28) guarantee that variables $DC^s_{k_j f_3}$ take the full value of DCP^s for the f_3 charging slots that $f_3 \leq FCS_{k_j z^s_{f_3}}$. Constraints (29) and (30) guarantee that the extra final slot adjacent to the ones that fully charge for DCP^s , takes the remaining energy value of $RE^s_{k_j}$, so that the total energy of all slots $DC^s_{k_j f_3}$, for which $z^s_{f_3} = f_1$, is equal to $EC^s_{k_j f_1}$. Respectively, Constraints (31) to (34) guarantee the same associations hold for fast chargers and respective variables. Based on these constraints, we can then calculate the energy consumption in kWh per demand charge period f_3 for slow chargers, fast chargers, and the whole charging stations network:

$$DEC_{f_3} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_1} DC^s_{k_j f_3} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_2} DC^h_{k_j f_3} \quad \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (35)$$

Equality (35) calculates the total energy per demand charge period $f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3$, from both slow and fast chargers.

3.2.6. Modeling of peak demand charge

The peak demand charge represents an additional surcharge for utilizing commercial electricity and is distinct from ToU tariffs. ToU Tariffs are based on the total electricity consumption measured in kilowatt-hours (kWh) per specific time periods. Unlike ToU tariffs, the demand charge is calculated based on the maximum power demand (measured in kilowatt), which can be recorded during any given demand charge period. This demand charge period can typically differ in terms of duration from that of the ToU Tariffs. For example, while ToU Tariffs can typically be hourly, the Peak Demand Charge period is usually shorter and can range from 1 min to 30 min. The primary purpose of demand charges is to influence commercial users' electricity consumption patterns to reduce peak power demand from the grid, and not the energy consumption during peak hours, as in the case of ToU Tariffs.

In our case, the formulation includes the cost stemming from the peak demand charges based on Eq. (2) and the second objective function \mathcal{O}_2 . The monetary cost DCR , which is an input parameter of the formulation, is based on the commercial contract between the electric bus services operator and the energy management authority. The calculation of the peak demand charge is based on the dependent variables $UD^s_{j f_3}$ and $UD^h_{j f_3}$, which take values according to Constraints (36) and (37):

$$M \cdot \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} u^s_{k_j z^s_{f_3}} \geq UD^s_{j f_3} \geq m \cdot \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} u^s_{k_j z^s_{f_3}} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_1, \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (36)$$

$$M \cdot \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} u^h_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} \geq UD^h_{j f_3} \geq m \cdot \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} u^h_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_2, \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (37)$$

In more detail, constraints (36) and (37) force $UD^s_{j f_3}$ and $UD^h_{j f_3}$ to take the value of one, if there is any bus assignment at a given charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$ during any $f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3$. For example, in the case that there is such an assignment at a slow charger (i.e. $u^s_{k_j z^s_{f_3}} = 1$), then constraint (36) forces respective variables $UD^s_{j f_3}$ to take a value between a very small number m and a very big number M , which due to the fact that $UD^s_{j f_3}$ is binary, will be the value of 1. In the opposite case, that there is no assignment during such period for either slow ($u^s_{k_j z^s_{f_3}} = 0$) or fast chargers ($u^h_{k_j z^h_{f_3}} = 0$), then constraints (36) and (37) force $UD^s_{j f_3}$ and $UD^h_{j f_3}$ to take the value of zero.

Based on this, the dependent variable IP^{\max} can be calculated according to the following constraints:

$$IP_{f_3}^s = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_1} (CP^s \cdot UD_{jf_3}^s) \quad \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (38)$$

$$IP_{f_3}^h = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_2} (CP^h \cdot UD_{jf_3}^h) \quad \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (39)$$

$$TIP_{f_3} = IP_{f_3}^s + IP_{f_3}^h \quad \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (40)$$

$$IP^{\max} \geq TIP_{f_3} \quad \forall f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3 \quad (41)$$

Eqs. (38) and (39) calculate quantities $IP_{f_3}^s$ and $IP_{f_3}^h$, which is the power consumed from the power grid from slow and fast chargers correspondingly for each demand charge time period f_3 . Then with Eq. (40), we calculate the total power TIP_{f_3} coming from both fast and chargers for each period f_3 , and finally, with inequality (41) we guarantee that IP^{\max} gets the maximum value from all demand charge time periods $f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3$.

3.2.7. Location capacity and coverage

Due to the locality of the already installed and candidate charging stations, several constraints are introduced into our formulation. Given the state of charge SOC_k for each trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ that has completed its operations and necessitates charging, there exists a minimum permissible state of charge SOC_k^{\min} for each trip k and a precise location of each prospective charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$, we can identify all potential chargers accessible to trip k . These feasible charger locations are those that trip k can access without its state of charge dropping below SOC_k^{\min} . Formally, a charger j is accessible to trip k if, and only if,

$$SOC_k - e \cdot q_{kj} \cdot d_{kj} \geq SOC_k^{\min} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (42)$$

In addition to this coverage constraint, we need to ascertain that the capacity constraints of the energy distribution grid for the local environment are considered. Each candidate location can have up to a specific number of chargers because of (i) the local energy distribution network capacity, and (ii) the space limitations at each location. Such a space-related constraint can be the limited number of parking spots for electric buses. For these reasons, we consider each location $v \in \mathcal{V}$ can have up to Cap_v number of chargers. Based on that, Constraint (43) is introduced to include this feature in our model.

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N} : \theta_j = v} x_j \leq Cap_v \quad \forall v \in \mathcal{V} \quad (43)$$

where θ_j parameter mapping the charging outlet $j \in \mathcal{N} (N1 \cup N2 \text{ and } N1 \cap N2 = 0)$ to the physical location $v \in \mathcal{V}$.

3.2.8. The bi-objective mixed integer-linear programming model

Considering the above, the problem of the Optimal Extensions of Electric Bus Charging Infrastructure, when considering charging scheduling and energy pricing, is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{Q}) : \\ \min \quad & \mathcal{O}_1, \mathcal{O}_2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \text{Constraints (6) to (43)} \end{aligned}$$

3.3. In search of pareto optimal solution fronts

Our problem and respective formulation have two objectives, \mathcal{O}_1 and \mathcal{O}_2 , which implies that solutions to the problem may be optimal with respect to the first objective \mathcal{O}_1 but not for the second objective \mathcal{O}_2 (and vice versa). The bi-objective nature of this problem creates a large decision space based on whether we are interested in optimizing for \mathcal{O}_1 or \mathcal{O}_2 , or potentially for a solution that addresses both objectives, with more or less emphasis on either of the objectives.

This trade-off between \mathcal{O}_1 and \mathcal{O}_2 needs to be analyzed and effectively presented to decision-makers. To address this need and provide applicable decision support to stakeholders in planning the public transport and energy grid networks, we extend the methodology to include a Multi-Objective Optimization Problem (MOOP) solution method for approximating the problem's Pareto Optimal Solutions front.

The Pareto front is defined as the group of solutions to the bi-objective problem that are not dominated by other optimal solutions with respect to either \mathcal{O}_1 and \mathcal{O}_2 . Suppose we denote as S the decision space for our problem that includes all solutions to the bi-objective problem, we are in search of the Pareto Optimal set S^* of non-dominated solutions s_j^* such that no other solution s_j satisfies both inequalities:

- $\mathcal{O}_i(s_j) + \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{O}_i} \leq \mathcal{O}_i(s_j^*) \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2\}$,
- $\mathcal{O}_i(s_j) + \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{O}_i} < \mathcal{O}_i(s_j^*)$ for at least one $i \in \{1, 2\}$

Where $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{O}_i}$ represents a minimum threshold in regards to the difference between the values of the two objective functions to be considered substantially dominant. According to related literature (Hwang and Masud, 1979; Gkiotsalitis, 2022), several types of MOOP methods exist that can be used for such this analysis, with the main categorization point being the involvement of decision maker (i.e. bus fleet operator) in the solution approach. In our case, and based on the ϵ -Constraint method, and without loss of generality, we solve m mathematical programs \tilde{Q}_m :

$$(\tilde{Q}_m) : \quad (44)$$

$$\min \mathcal{O}_2$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathcal{O}_1 \leq \epsilon_m \quad (45)$$

Constraints (6) to (43)

Set $\epsilon = \epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \dots, \epsilon_m$ of m parameters, serve as the right-hand side (upper bounds) in constraint (45) of the mathematical programs \tilde{Q}_m . If the values on the right-hand side $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_m$ are predetermined based on input from the decision-maker, then we are using an *a priori* ϵ -constraint method. However, in our case, we can compute a potentially sufficient subset of the Pareto front without input from the decision-maker by varying these constants and solving problem (44) multiple times. In this case, the ϵ -constraint method is used as an *a posteriori* approach where the results are presented to the decision makers, based on which they can make an informed decision. To determine the exact values of set ϵ , the initial problem \tilde{Q} is solved twice, once for \mathcal{O}_1 and once for \mathcal{O}_2 . The resulting values for objective \mathcal{O}_1 can then be used as the two extreme elements of set ϵ .

4. Numerical experiments

This section presents the numerical results of applying our methodology to derive effective decision support based on real-world data. The results are organized into six subsections, with the first focusing on an explainable toy network with open data from Manhattan, New York, United States of America (USA). The second subsection presents a case study with higher bus line coverage focused on the central area of Limassol, Cyprus. The third subsection gives the computational analysis of the proposed model, and fourth subsection provides a sensitivity analysis. A fifth subsection describes a multi-stage extension experiment where the charging station network is extended in stages. A final subsection is given where implications from the model application are summarized.

Several parameters related to charging stations and the electric buses specification are shared across all subsections and respective numerical results. More specifically, and according to parameters defined for the fleet as described in Section 3.2 and appendix Table A.1, the buses' maximum battery capacity SOC_k^{\max} is considered to be 350 kWh, while the minimum allowable has been considered to be 20% of the max capacity at $SOC_k^{\min} = 70$ kWh. The consumption of the buses has been considered to be at the value provided by their manufacturer at $e = 0.72$ kWh per kilometer. The power output of the slow chargers has been considered to be $CP^s = 150$ kW, while the power output for fast chargers is considered to be $CP^f = 300$ kW. The cost for installing a slow charger is considered $b_1 = 30,000$ €, while for fast chargers is considered $b_2 = 50,000$ €. The duration of the time slots for both applications is considered $df_1 = 120$ min for slow chargers, $df_2 = 60$ min for fast chargers, and $df_3 = 15$ min for the demand period of the energy operator.

The MILP model further relies on two types of energy pricing datasets: ToU tariffs and demand charge costs. Despite the limited availability of such data, both approaches in our study utilize real-world datasets. In the toy network application for New York, ToU tariffs were extracted from hourly demand data, while in the Limassol case study, they were obtained from the relevant public authorities. The input data for bus networks and public transport services are openly accessible through public transport operators' websites. Each subsection below includes hyperlinks, detailed information, and bus network visualizations.

Finally, all experiments in the results section were conducted on a Lenovo ThinkSystem ST250 server equipped with an Intel Xeon E-2356G processor and 32 Gigabytes (GB) of RAM. For the solution of the MILP model instances, the academic version of Gurobi Optimizer 11.0 was used. Each problem instance was solved to global optimality with respect to the objective function(s) considered for that specific problem instance in each respective case study.

4.1. Experimentation on a toy network

For this first application of the ϵ -constraint method and the MILP model on the toy network from Manhattan island in New York (NY), our focus has been to provide a reproducible and comprehensive small-scale case study. Therefore, all the data within this experiment section come from a snapshot from May 2017 and are openly available.

More specifically, we were able to produce a ToU Tariff daily profile by combining Hourly Load data from the NY Independent System Operator (NYISO)⁴ together with average prices per kWh from the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics⁵. The load data from NYISO for May 2017 have been analyzed to determine their statistical average values, which were then combined with the corresponding average kWh price for the same period to estimate the ToU tariffs. The final ToU tariffs were subsequently used in the experiments, as presented in Fig. A.1 in the appendix. For the Peak Demand Charges, the pricing has been extracted from a report from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory⁶.

⁴ Hourly Load data from the New York Independent System Operator, [Website](#)

⁵ Average energy prices per kWh for May 2017 from the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, [Website](#)

⁶ Maximum, average, and median demand charges for New York from a report from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory from 2017, [Website](#)

Fig. 4. The M1 and M2 bus lines in Manhattan, NY.

The NY bus network data for the period under study is also openly available as a General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) feed from TransitFeeds⁷ and New York's Metropolitan Transport Authority (MTA). The case study has focused on bus lines M1 and M2 that run in Manhattan, NY, as seen in Fig. 4. The bus depot locations can be extracted from openly available information⁸.

The application of the model also requires the number of buses and the respective services when the buses need to be charged. Based on these two pieces of information, one set and two problem parameters can be defined. These are the set \mathcal{K} , and parameters τ_k and d_{kj} . Since this toy network application focuses on the services offered from two-way fixed bus lines for a single weekday, the above sets and parameters can be extracted from the GTFS feed. We have implemented and applied the Single Depot Vehicle Scheduling Problem (SD-VSP) model as defined previously in the literature. The SD-VSP result is the maximum number of bus reuses for the daily services of a single two-way fixed bus line, which implies the minimum number of buses required. This minimum number of buses can be used to generate set \mathcal{K} . This result can then be utilized in combination with a GTFS feed reverse lookup routine where we extract: (i) the last stop coordinates from the *stops.txt*, based on which we calculate the distances matrix d_{ij} , and (ii) τ_k , extracted from the *stop_times.txt* file of the GTFS feed. Based on this discussion, the temporal input parameters for the toy network are given in the appendix Table A.2.

A final input parameter for the toy network is the initial set of chargers that existed before this extension of the charging stations network. We consider that three slow chargers are already installed at each of the locations #1 and #2 for the toy network. The locations of the candidate chargers, along with the final stops for each bus trip of the bus lines, can be found in Fig. 5.

From the application of the ϵ -constraint method, our MILP model is solved for different values of ϵ and the input data from the Manhattan area, NY. As discussed in Section 3.3, the starting ϵ_1 and ending ϵ_m values are acquired from the values of objective \mathcal{O}_1 when formulation \bar{Q} is solved for the first (\mathcal{O}_1) and second (\mathcal{O}_2) objectives, respectively. The main outcome is given in Fig. 6, which presents the solution values of the second objective \mathcal{O}_2 (y-axis) for the different ϵ values (x-axis). In Fig. 7, a diagram of all the solutions acquired from the application of the ϵ -constraint method is given, plotted with the values of \mathcal{O}_1 across the x-axis and the values of \mathcal{O}_2 for across the y-axis. The different Pareto optimal solutions are highlighted in various colors, as shown in the legend. The solutions acquired by applying the ϵ -constraint method that do not belong to the Pareto optimal front are plotted with gray. Overall, the diagram of Fig. 7 includes nine Pareto optimal solutions acquired between $\epsilon_1 = 229.61$ and $\epsilon_m = 419.8$. For the Pareto dominance between solutions, we considered that for a solution to dominate over another, it has to have at least one minute less of deadhead time in \mathcal{O}_1 or a decrease of at least 100 dollars in total monetary cost in \mathcal{O}_2 . Based on our definition of Pareto dominance in Section 3.3, this means that we considered $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{O}_1} = 1$ and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{O}_2} = 100$.

The detailed assignments of buses to chargers and time slots are provided for all Pareto solutions in a tabular format. Pareto optimal solution one with the least deadhead time is given in Table 2, and Pareto solution nine with the least monetary cost is

⁷ TransitFeeds platform with the MTA GTFS from May 2017, [Website](#)

⁸ MTA Bus depot locations on Wikipedia, [Website](#)

Fig. 5. The candidate charger locations (blue markers) and the bus trip services' last stops (orange markers) for the Manhattan area, NY.

Fig. 6. Results of the e-constraint method for the Manhattan, NY toy network.

shown in Table 3. The rest of Pareto optimal solutions for the Manhattan toy network (Pareto solutions two to eight) are given in the appendix Tables A.3, A.4, A.5, A.6, A.7, A.8 and A.9. Although the modeling horizon extends from 06:00 to 24:00, the results tables exclude time slots that do not have assigned buses. Furthermore, while each bus is allocated to a single charging slot, certain buses occupy two consecutive one-hour time slots in the results tables due to the fact that f_1 time slots have a duration of two hours.

In Pareto solution one, the values for the objectives are $\mathcal{O}_1 = 229.61$ and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 351,269.55$. In this case, the MILP model selects a charging station network of thirteen chargers to cover the demand for bus trips, selecting seven slow and six fast chargers. Seven of the thirteen chargers included in Pareto solution one are new extensions to the charging network. The new proposed charging stations are the fast chargers at locations #1, #2, #3 and #6, as well as one extra slow charger at location #6. Pareto optimal solution nine is given in Table 3, where the value of the first objective $\mathcal{O}_1 = 375.77$ min and the value for the second objective being $\mathcal{O}_2 = 171,301.55$ dollars. Pareto optimal solution nine for the Manhattan toy network proposes a charging station network of nine chargers overall, three of which are fast. These three fast chargers of the proposed charging stations network are also the new ones as compared to the already existing ones. While this solution substantially decreases the monetary cost (i.e., 51.3%) as compared to Pareto solution #1, at the same time, it considerably increases deadhead time compared to the Pareto optimal solution one (i.e., 63.65%). This is because, in addition to the already existing charging stations network at locations #1 and #2, Pareto solution nine proposes the installation of only three new chargers (fast chargers), while Pareto solution #1 proposes the installation of seven additional chargers, six of which are fast and one is slow. Other alternative Pareto optimal solutions exist to the problem, whose trade-offs between the two objectives can be further noticed in Fig. 7 and Tables A.3 to A.9 in the appendix.

Fig. 7. The approximation of the Pareto optimal front of solutions for the case study on the Manhattan, New York bus network.

Table 2

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 1 of the toy network with $\phi_1 = 229.61$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\phi_2 = 351,269.55$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00	
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	–	–
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	–	–
1	Fast	4	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	51	54
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	–	–
1	Fast	6	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	53
2	Slow	7	–	33	33	36	36	31	31	16	16	–	–	–
2	Fast	8	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	47	–	21	–	–
2	Slow	9	–	3	3	1	1	39	39	23	23	–	–	–
2	Slow	11	–	30	30	5	5	15	15	17	17	–	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	7	–	13	12	20	19	24	28	29	–
3	Fast	16	–	–	6	8	10	14	18	22	26	25	27	–
6	Slow	31	–	–	–	–	–	41	41	–	–	49	49	–
6	Fast	32	–	32	34	37	–	40	43	–	48	50	52	–

Table 3

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 9 of the toy network with $\phi_1 = 375.77$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\phi_2 = 171,301.55$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00		
1	Slow	1	3	3	5	5	11	11	44	44	49	49	–	–
1	Slow	3	31	31	–	–	41	41	45	45	51	51	–	–
1	Slow	5	1	1	4	4	–	–	46	46	50	50	–	–
2	Slow	7	33	33	36	36	38	38	17	17	16	16	–	–
2	Slow	9	30	30	9	9	15	15	42	42	21	21	–	–
2	Slow	11	2	2	35	35	39	39	47	47	23	23	–	–
3	Fast	16	–	6	8	13	14	18	22	25	27	54	–	–
3	Fast	18	–	7	–	10	12	20	19	26	28	29	–	–
6	Fast	34	32	34	37	–	40	43	24	48	52	53	–	–

Our approximation of the Pareto front for the bi-objective formulation of the toy network of Manhattan, NY, reveals several insights that could be used to plan the extension of the charging stations network. For example, from Pareto solution one, a team of transport planners and policy makers can deduce that the minimum deadhead time can be 229.61 min for the two bus lines and their trips, which would require the most upfront investments and daily operating costs. On the other hand, if the decision makers want to minimize the monetary cost, the most suitable solution would be Pareto solution nine, with a total deadhead time of 375.77 min and a smaller charging stations network of nine chargers. In addition to these insights, one may deduce that some Pareto solutions can

Fig. 8. The bus lines considered for the case study in Limassol, Cyprus.

be more valuable than others. For instance, Pareto solutions two, three and four provide significant cost reductions with relatively modest increases in deadhead time when compared to Pareto optimal solution #1. This is evident from the steep initial slope of the Pareto front, as seen in Fig. 7. Moving beyond Pareto solution four, the curve begins to level off, indicating a diminishing return on cost savings for additional increases in deadhead time. In this toy network scenario, one can observe that Pareto solutions two, three and four offer a reasonable balance, optimizing for monetary cost without disproportionately increasing the deadhead time.

4.2. A case study on Limassol, Cyprus

Next, we present an application of the ϵ -constraint method and the MILP model in the urban center of Limassol, Cyprus. In this case study, we focus on more bus lines than the toy network in Manhattan, New York. The modeling approach is applied on data from bus lines 3, 4, 5 (and 5B), 7, 9 (and 9 A), and 11, which can be found on the public transport operator's website.⁹ The network of bus lines considered for Limassol, Cyprus, is depicted in Fig. 8.

As for the initial set-up of the chargers, we consider that four slow chargers are already established. Three are located at candidate charger location #1, and one is located at candidate charging location #2. At most, up to three slow and three fast chargers are allowed at each location. The candidate charger locations and the last stops of the bus trips that need recharging can be found in Fig. 9. The data about ToU Tariffs and demand charges in Limassol have been acquired after direct communication with the Electricity Authority of Cyprus.

Similarly to the toy network, the case study focuses on the trips offered within a single weekday. To extract the number of buses required to run the services, we apply an SD-VSP model, which gives the minimum number of buses (i.e. vehicles) needed to run the trips. This value is used to create the formulation's set \mathcal{K} . Based on a reverse lookup routine on the GTFS feed, we extract the location and time of arrival τ_k at the last stops of each bus trip, as it can be viewed in appendix Table A.10.

Using the ϵ -constraint method for this case study, our MILP model is solved for different values of ϵ and the input data from Limassol, Cyprus. The results are plotted in Figs. 10 and 11. In Fig. 10, one may notice the values of the second objective \mathcal{O}_2 in dollars across the y -axis and the corresponding values of ϵ (i.e. maximum deadhead time) are given across the x -axis. Similarly to

⁹ Limassol Public Transport Operator's website, [Website](#)

Fig. 9. The candidate charger locations (blue markers) and the bus trip services' last stops (orange markers) for the Limassol, Cyprus case study.

Fig. 10. Results of the ϵ -constraint method for the case study of the Limassol, Cyprus area.

the toy network, in Fig. 11, all solutions derived from applying the ϵ -constraint method are plotted according to the values of the two objectives of the problem. The first objective \mathcal{O}_1 of total deadhead time is plotted across the x -axis in minutes, while the second objective \mathcal{O}_2 remains at the y -axis.

According to the results, ten Pareto optimal solutions exist for the problem under study. These solutions are represented with distinct colors in Fig. 11 and are detailed in Tables 4 to 7, as well as in Appendix Tables A.11 to A.16. Similarly to the toy network

Fig. 11. The approximation of the Pareto optimal front of solutions for the case study on the network of Limassol, Cyprus.

application, the results tables provide the allocation of buses to chargers and time slots for all Pareto solutions. Although the modeling horizon spans from 06:00 to 24:00, time slots without assigned buses are omitted from the tables. Moreover, while each bus is assigned to a single charging slot (either for slow or fast charging), some buses appear in two consecutive one-hour time slots in the results tables due to the two-hour duration of f_1 time slots in this case study.

As it may be noticed from the figure and the respective tables, optimal solutions for Limassol differ in terms of the number of chargers they are proposing, the types of chargers, and the charging schedule. Starting with the first Pareto solution (Table 4), it proposes the installation of nine chargers overall, four of which are fast. The chargers are located at locations #1, #2, #3, #4 and #6, and the solution derives a deadhead time of $\mathcal{O}_1 = 56.05$ min and a total cost of $\mathcal{O}_2 = 242,275.44$ dollars. Pareto optimal solutions two, three and four provide a substantial decrease regarding the second objective \mathcal{O}_2 but an increase regarding the deadhead time \mathcal{O}_1 . As it can be noticed in Tables 5–7, they all propose the same number of chargers, which is eight, but include different types of chargers.

In particular, Pareto solution two (Table 5) proposes a network of eight chargers, out of which half are fast and half are slow. This second Pareto solution offers a deadhead time of $\mathcal{O}_1 = 59.91$ min and a total cost of $\mathcal{O}_2 = 212,275.64$ dollars. It can be observed that the deadhead time in the second Pareto-optimal solution is higher compared to the first solution while also incurring a substantially reduced monetary cost. Continuing by comparing Tables 6 and 7 for Pareto solutions three and four, one may notice that these two solutions are not that different to Pareto solution two. Pareto solution three proposes a total of eight charging stations, three of which are designated as fast chargers. In comparison to Pareto solution two, this configuration includes one fewer fast charger, which is achieved by allocating a slow charger at location four instead of a fast charger (that is proposed for that location in Pareto optimal solution two). In this way, Pareto solution three is able to provide a lower monetary cost but at an increased deadhead time for the fleet of electric buses while still maintaining the same number of chargers as Pareto optimal solution two. Pareto solution three achieves a deadhead time of $\mathcal{O}_1 = 66.41$ and a cost of $\mathcal{O}_2 = 192,275.96$ dollars. Similarly to Pareto solutions two and three, Pareto solution four (Table 7) also proposes a network of eight chargers with a deadhead time of $\mathcal{O}_1 = 78.83$ min and a cost of $\mathcal{O}_2 = 172,276.42$ dollars. Pareto solution four, in comparison to Pareto solutions two and three, primarily involves the replacement of the fast charger at location #6 with a slow charger. This adjustment contributes to a further reduction in overall costs while still maintaining only a marginal increase in deadhead time relative to the other two solutions that are proposing eight chargers in total.

The Pareto front for the Limassol case study includes six more Pareto solutions, as they can be found in the appendix Tables A.11 to A.16. Pareto solutions five to nine, which are given in appendix Tables A.11 to A.15, all propose a network of seven chargers, which means proposing three new chargers in addition to the already pre-existing ones. These five Pareto solutions alternate between the types of chargers that should be installed, as in the case of Pareto solutions two, three and four, but they also differentiate according to the location where each slow or fast charger must be installed. In that regard, Pareto solutions five (appendix Table A.11) and six (appendix Table A.12) propose the installation of three additional fast chargers, with both solutions proposing the installation of fast chargers at locations #3 and #6, but with solution five installing a fast charger at location #4, where solution six proposes a fast charger at location #1. Similarly, Pareto solutions seven (appendix Table A.13) and eight (appendix Table A.14) propose a network of seven chargers overall, two of which are fast. Pareto solution eight utilizes locations #1, #2, #3 and #6, with the fast chargers being placed at locations #1 and #6, while Pareto solution seven utilizes the same locations and, additionally, selects to place the fast charger at locations #3 and #4.

Table 4

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 1 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 56.05$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 242,275.44$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	29	29	9	9	24	24	26	26	34	34	13	13
1	Slow	3	–	–	30	30	10	10	20	20	4	4	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	2	2	16	16	27	27	–	–
1	Fast	6	–	14	–	–	15	6	–	–	–	–	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Slow	13	–	–	5	5	–	–	17	17	–	–	–	–
3	Fast	18	–	–	–	–	–	–	7	11	8	12	–	–
4	Fast	20	–	–	1	32	33	–	–	3	–	–	–	–
6	Fast	32	–	22	23	31	–	25	–	–	–	28	–	–

Table 5

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 2 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 59.91$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 212,275.64$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	29	29	–	–	10	10	26	26	4	4	13	13
1	Fast	2	–	14	9	2	–	6	16	–	–	–	–	–
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	24	24	20	20	27	27	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	30	30	15	15	–	–	34	34	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	18	–	–	5	–	–	–	11	17	8	12	–	–
4	Fast	24	–	–	1	32	33	–	–	3	–	–	–	–
6	Fast	36	–	22	–	23	31	–	25	7	–	–	28	–

Finally, Pareto solutions nine and ten exhibit considerable differences not only from each other but also from the rest of the Pareto front. Pareto solution nine proposes seven chargers overall with only one fast charger at location #4. As observed in appendix Table A.15, this solution achieves the lowest monetary cost, $\mathcal{O}_2 = 122,277.62$, among all Pareto solutions with seven chargers (Pareto solutions five to nine). However, this cost efficiency is accompanied by an increase in deadhead time, reaching $\mathcal{O}_1 = 115.98$. Pareto solution ten (appendix Table A.16) is the only one proposing six chargers overall, with the installation of two new fast chargers at locations #1 and #6. It achieves the least amount of monetary cost $\mathcal{O}_2 = 112,278.89$ but has the maximum amount of deadhead time $\mathcal{O}_1 = 125.03$ out of all the Pareto optimal solutions.

The approximation of the Pareto front for the bi-objective formulation of the bus network for Limassol, Cyprus, reveals several insights. The first is that for the network under consideration and given the frequency of the trips as they are currently made, the buses' charging needs do not require installing what would be considered an extensive network of charging stations. As seen in Pareto optimal solution ten, only two additional fast chargers, in combination with the pre-existing ones, can satisfy the charging demand for bus lines 3, 4, 5 (and 5B), 7, 9 (and 9 A), and 11. On a second level, the application of the method proposed in this article identifies ten alternative optimal configurations of chargers (i.e. Pareto optimal solutions), with no single configuration universally dominating the rest of the solutions for both of the objectives considered. The selection of the most suitable configuration depends significantly on the priorities and objectives of the respective public transport operator. Nonetheless, certain Pareto solutions present more favorable trade-offs than others. For instance, Pareto solutions two and three achieve notable reductions in monetary cost compared to Pareto solution one with only a relatively small increase in deadhead time. In contrast, when compared to Pareto solutions four, five, and six, the reduction in monetary cost is less pronounced, while the associated increase in deadhead time is more substantial.

4.3. Computational complexity of proposed MILP model

Next, the computational complexity of the model proposed in this article is examined. The complexity is primarily influenced by the number of buses requiring recharging \mathcal{K} , the number of candidate charger locations in set \mathcal{V} , and the potential chargers per location in set \mathcal{N} . As \mathcal{K} increases, the number of constraints and decision variables grows, expanding the solution space. Similarly, a larger set of candidate locations (set \mathcal{V}) and a higher number of candidate chargers (set \mathcal{N}) add to the combinatorial complexity of the problem instance to be solved.

The computational complexity of the model is examined based on forty-seven synthetic problem instances. To define these synthetic problem instances, an experimental design approach is followed based on which the sizes of sets \mathcal{K} , \mathcal{V} , and \mathcal{N} are defined. The approach is primarily focused on increasing the problem size by expanding the number of buses that need to recharge, as considered in set \mathcal{K} . The sets \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{N} are adjusted to accommodate the charging needs of fleet \mathcal{K} for each problem instance while

Table 6

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 3 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 66.41$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 192,275.96$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	29	29	–	–	2	2	16	16	34
1	Slow	3	–	–	30	30	10	10	20	20	27	27	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	32	32	24	24	26	26	4	4	–	–
1	Fast	6	–	14	9	–	15	6	–	–	–	–	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	18	–	–	–	5	–	–	11	17	8	12	–	–
4	Slow	21	–	–	1	1	33	33	3	3	–	–	–	–
6	Fast	32	–	22	23	31	–	–	25	7	–	–	28	–

Table 7

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 4 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 78.83$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 172,276.42$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	–	–	30	30	2	2	26	26	–
1	Slow	3	–	–	1	1	10	10	7	7	34	34	–	–
1	Fast	4	29	14	–	24	6	16	–	–	27	–	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	9	9	15	15	20	20	4	4	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	16	–	22	5	–	–	–	11	17	12	8	–	–
4	Slow	23	–	–	32	32	33	33	3	3	–	–	–	–
6	Slow	35	–	–	23	23	31	31	25	25	–	–	28	28

Fig. 12. Number of bus trips $|\mathcal{K}|$ and the number of charger installation options $|\mathcal{N}|$ for each of the 47 problem instances.

ensuring the feasibility of the solution. Specifically, if the number of considered buses in set \mathcal{K} increases to the extent that the available charger installation options are insufficient to meet the charging demand, the problem may be rendered infeasible. For that reason, in this computational analysis, as we increase the size of set \mathcal{K} , we also have to increase the sizes of sets \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{N} accordingly. This experimental design approach can be conceptualized based on a ‘supply’ and ‘demand’ dynamic, wherein the buses generate the charging demand, and the chargers supply the required charging (locations, chargers and charging slots). The sizes of the problem instances start from a set of buses $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, 20\}$ that require charging, $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ physical locations for charging stations and $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, 8\}$ available chargers. We then increase the sizes of the instances progressively until going up to the size of $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, 480\}$, $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, 18\}$ and $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, 108\}$. Figs. 12, 13, and 14 present the corresponding results for each problem instance, considering various combinations of values for sets \mathcal{K} , \mathcal{V} , and \mathcal{N} .

The computational analysis results demonstrate that the proposed MILP model can be solved within relatively short computational times. For smaller problem instances, such as Problem 15, which includes up to one-hundred sixty bus trips, four candidate charging station locations, and eight potential chargers, the solution is obtained in under ten seconds. As the problem size increases,

Fig. 13. Number of charging station physical locations $|\mathcal{V}|$ considered for each of the 47 problem instances.

Fig. 14. Computation time for each of the 47 problem instances.

even complex instances, such as Problem 40, which consists of four-hundred and ten bus trips, fourteen candidate locations, and eighty-four charger installation options, are solved in just over four minutes. This remains a reasonable computational time given that this type of model needs to be run once in an ex-ante assessment planning phase. While the computational analysis indicates that even Problem 47 is solvable within practical time limits, it has revealed a limitation of this model which comes to the fact that it is resource intensive when it comes to the size of the computer short-term memory (i.e. RAM memory) that is required for it to run. Problem instances for more than four-hundred and eighty buses exceeded the memory capacity of our computing system (32 GB RAM), highlighting that more resources would be needed to run bigger problem instances.

These experimental results confirm that our problem formulation is efficiently solvable using exact methods (Branch-and-Cut) within acceptable computational times, making it suitable for real-world applications, particularly in medium-sized urban municipal areas. Additionally, with enhanced computing resources (e.g., systems with more than 32 GB RAM), the model can be extended to solve even larger problem instances beyond the size of Problem 47.

4.4. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of parameter variations on the solutions generated by the proposed bi-objective MILP model. By systematically adjusting key model inputs, this analysis provides valuable insights into how such changes influence the optimality of the solutions. In the context of the proposed research and related transportation science problems, travel times are anticipated to play a critical role in shaping routing, scheduling, and overall system performance (Börjesson, 2014). Given

Fig. 15. The sensitivity analysis for the Pareto fronts of the Limassol case study when four different levels of travel times are considered.

its inherent variability due to factors such as traffic conditions, weather fluctuations, and infrastructure constraints (Guessous et al., 2014), analyzing the sensitivity of travel times allows for a deeper understanding of their effects on the solutions derived from the MILP model and the ϵ -constraint method.

To this end, the results of the Limassol case study were analyzed under varying scenarios of travel time fluctuations relative to the standard travel times. Specifically, four alternative travel time scenarios were examined: (i) the standard travel time, (ii) 80% of the standard travel time, (iii) 120% of the standard travel time, and (iv) 140% of the standard travel time.

As it can be noticed from Fig. 15, the increase of travel time results in a near-linear effect in the values of objective \mathcal{O}_1 and \mathcal{O}_2 with the Pareto optimal solutions for the four scenarios being equivalent in terms of number of Pareto solutions and the Pareto solutions themselves (location and charger selection). The primary distinction between the scenarios has been observed in the charging schedule assignments of the buses, which results in only a marginal impact on the objective function values. Consequently, this leads to slight variations in the plotted Pareto solutions. The authors' analysis attributes this near-linear effect to the relatively small geographic scope of the Limassol case study, which is concentrated in the city center of a medium-sized urban environment. This localized context provides sufficient flexibility for optimal decision-making across all travel time scenarios, thereby mitigating the impact of travel time variability on the results.

These initial results, however, do not imply that the model is insensitive to travel time variability. To thoroughly evaluate the model's sensitivity, a larger-scale problem is introduced as a test case for a wider area of Cyprus. This larger-scale synthetic scenario involves a fleet of one hundred buses, five candidate locations, each accommodating two potential fast chargers and two potential slow chargers (resulting in a total of twenty candidate chargers overall). This problem instance creates a rather confined solution space for the charging demand, exposing the method's Pareto optimal solutions to greater variability according to the travel times fluctuations. Sets \mathcal{K} , \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{N} for this wider scale case study are randomly generated, utilizing the same software routines that have been used to generate synthetic problem instances for Section 4.3 and the computational analysis of the model.

As observed in Fig. 16, the Pareto fronts in the larger-scale synthetic scenario exhibit substantial differences, not only in terms of Pareto optimal solutions (location, charger and charging scheduling assignments) but also in the number of Pareto solutions identified for different levels of travel time and their respective Pareto fronts. For example, the 80% scenario includes eight Pareto optimal solutions, while the 140% scenario includes thirteen Pareto optimal solutions.

From this sensitivity analysis, one may deduce that the problem of extending electric bus charging station networks, as defined in this study, is relatively insensitive to variations in travel times when applied to small-scale problem instances, such as the city center of Limassol. However, when scaling the problem to larger networks, variations in travel times could introduce increased complexity, necessitating the consideration of multiple Pareto fronts and solutions. In addition, it was noted that lower travel times (80% scenario) resulted in fewer Pareto optimal solutions compared to the other scenarios with greater travel times, but this insight requires further research in order to be generalizable.

4.5. Experiments on a multi-stage extension of an electric bus charging network

To further investigate the solution space of the problem, a multi-stage experiment is conducted to examine the effects of progressively expanding the network of charging stations for electric buses. Specifically, the experiment examines how imposing a limit on the number of chargers installed at each stage affects the model's behavior and solutions. Additionally, the results are compared to the unconstrained case, where no such limit is imposed, allowing the model to compute a globally optimal solution, which serves as a benchmark.

Fig. 16. The sensitivity analysis for the Pareto fronts of the larger-scale synthetic experiment when four different levels of travel times are considered.

Table 8

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the globally optimal solution to the problem instance of Limassol when considering only one objective \mathcal{O}_1 and $CS^{\max} = M$. The objective function value for this solution is $\mathcal{O}_1 = 56.05$.

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	29	29	14	14	15	15	10	10	2	2	27	27
1	Slow	3	–	–	9	9	6	6	16	16	4	4	13	13
1	Slow	5	–	–	30	30	24	24	20	20	34	34	26	26
2	Slow	7	–	–	–	–	–	–	18	18	21	21	19	19
3	Fast	14	–	–	–	–	5	–	11	–	8	17	7	12
4	Fast	24	–	–	–	32	–	–	–	–	–	1	33	3
6	Fast	36	–	22	–	–	–	–	25	–	–	28	23	31

In this section, we solve the MILP model according to the first objective, which is the minimization of the deadhead times for the electric bus fleet:

$$(\tilde{Q}_{ms}) : \tag{46}$$

$$\min \mathcal{O}_1$$

$$\text{s.t. Constraints (6) to (43)}$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_5 \cup \mathcal{N}_6} x_j \leq CS^{\max} \tag{47}$$

where the parameter CS^{\max} is used to indicate the maximum number of new charging stations to be installed in any of the considered locations \mathcal{V} . As a benchmark for this multi-stage extension experiment, we consider the solution to the problem of extending the already existing charging stations network, exactly as it has been referenced in Section 4.2. This means solving Problem (46) without constraint (47), or equivalently when $CS^{\max} = M$. In this way, we derive the globally optimal solution to the problem for the minimum deadhead, which is depicted in Table 8.

Considering that in the Limassol case study, there is an already established charging station network of four slow chargers at locations #1 and #2 (three chargers at #1 and one charger at #2), the globally optimal solution proposes the installation of three additional fast chargers at locations #3, #4 and #6. Given that the globally optimal solution includes three additional chargers, we attempt to solve three more problem instances for extending the network of Limassol in three stages. In each stage, the MILP model is solved with the objective of minimizing deadhead times according to \mathcal{O}_1 and when enabling the extension of up to one, two, and three chargers accordingly.

In a first stage extension, when the model is allowed to install just one extra charger as an initial planning step, the solver fails to find a feasible solution, rendering the problem an infeasible one. This result might be expected, as this infeasibility suggests that the CS network setup attempted (four existing slow chargers, plus a new additional fast or slow charger at any of the candidate charger locations) cannot meet the charging demand of thirty-four buses of the eight bus lines of Limassol, given the constraints of the problem (mainly concerning the charging scheduling requirements).

Table 9

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the globally optimal solution to the problem instance of Limassol when considering only one objective \mathcal{O}_1 and $CS^{max} = 2$. The objective function value for this solution is $\mathcal{O}_1 = 97.77$.

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	29	29	9	9	10	10	2	2	6
1	Slow	3	–	–	14	14	15	15	16	16	34	34	13	13
1	Slow	5	–	–	30	30	24	24	26	26	20	20	4	4
2	Slow	7	–	–	–	–	–	–	19	19	21	21	18	18
4	Slow	19	–	–	1	1	–	–	33	33	32	32	3	3
6	Fast	36	–	22	23	31	5	25	7	17	12	11	28	8

Table 10

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the globally optimal solution to the problem instance of Limassol when considering only one objective \mathcal{O}_1 and $CS^{max} = 3$. The objective function value for this solution is $\mathcal{O}_1 = 56.05$.

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	29	29	9	9	10	10	24	24	27
1	Slow	3	–	–	30	30	2	2	15	15	4	4	26	26
1	Slow	5	–	–	14	14	6	6	20	20	34	34	16	16
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	5	–	–	–	7	–	12	8	11	17
4	Fast	24	–	–	32	33	–	–	3	–	–	–	1	–
6	Fast	36	–	22	23	31	–	25	–	–	–	28	–	–

As a second stage experiment, it is attempted to solve Problem (46) when $CS^{max} = 2$, meaning that the model’s solution can include up to two new chargers, each being either slow or fast. As can be viewed in Table 9, in this case, the model’s solution includes two additional new chargers, one slow charger at charger location #4 and one fast charger at location #6. One may notice that while charging the fast charger at location #6 is part of the globally optimal solution (Table 8), in this case the model selects a slow charger at location #4 instead of a fast one (as it selects in globally optimal solution). While this can be viewed as a differentiation to the globally optimal solution, it actually is not, because in Problem (46) we are solving towards the minimization of deadhead time, and a slow or fast charger can equally create the same deadhead time in the problem solution given that it utilizes the same location as a fast charger.

A third stage is solved for Problem (46) with $CS^{max} = 3$. The solution is presented in Table 10, where three fast chargers are selected. These three chargers and their locations are the ones included in the globally optimal solution, with the solution derived in this third stage having the same objective function value ($\mathcal{O}_1 = 56.05$) as the globally optimal solution. One minor difference between the globally optimal solution and the problem instance where Problem (46) is constrained to have up to three chargers can be located at the charging assignment of electric buses to the chargers, which can be due to the numerical instability of the solver.

Overall, the findings from this multi-stage experiment indicate a consistent pattern in model outcomes when the expansion of the charging station network is implemented in multiple stages. More specifically, when comparing the global solution of the unrestricted problem, it becomes evident that three fast chargers are proposed, which also appear in the solutions to the two feasible sub-problems where the network extension is considered for up to two or three chargers. In the case where the model is constrained to include up to one new charger, we notice that the problem instance is rendered infeasible, meaning potentially that a multi-stage extension of a CS network has to consider charging demand by the buses and potential energy supply by the grid at all stages.

4.6. Implications for the strategic planning of the extensions of electric bus charging infrastructure

Several considerations emerge from the application of the ϵ -constraint method and the MILP model, as presented in the results section. First, given the number of Pareto solutions in each case study, one can understand that the problem of extending an already existing charging station network is indeed subject to a trade-off between electric buses deadheading times and the cost that the bus operator is willing to pay. The application of the method derives nine Pareto solutions in the first case study in Manhattan, New York and ten for Limassol, Cyprus. These solutions are non-dominated, meaning each one offers unique advantages and disadvantages in the electric bus network extension planning and operation.

One may further notice that the Pareto fronts of solutions to the optimal extension problem are characterized mainly by alternating between the number of chargers and types of chargers (slow/fast). This can be particularly noticed in the case of Manhattan, NY and bus lines M1 and M2, where nine Pareto solutions are calculated, covering the same charging demand but combining different numbers of chargers to be installed with different types of chargers. Similar insights can be drawn from the case of Limassol and its Pareto optimal solutions, where the ten solutions differentiate in terms of the number of chargers and charger type, but they also may differentiate in terms of selected location. In other words, two solutions may have the same number of chargers and types, but the difference can be mainly noticed in the locations selected. Such Pareto solutions in the Limassol case

study are Pareto solutions five (appendix Table A.11) and six (appendix Table A.12) that both propose the installation of three additional fast chargers, with both solutions proposing the installation of fast chargers at locations #3 and #6, but with solution five installing a fast charger at location #4, where solution six proposes a fast charger at location #1.

With regard to selecting a specific Pareto-optimal solution as an intervention in an existing network, this methodology offers considerably valuable support for planning professionals and policymakers. By leveraging the scientific evidence that can come from the re-application of the methodology presented in this article, they can make informed decisions regarding the extension of the charging network. Using the real-world case of Limassol, Cyprus, as a reference, the ten alternative Pareto-optimal solutions derived from the case study provide decision-makers with sufficient options to evaluate alongside additional factors, such as land use considerations, parking space at bus depots or energy grid connectivity opportunities.

As a final consideration, the sensitivity analysis of the model for Limassol suggests that the Pareto-optimal solutions for this specific case are relatively robust to variations in travel time that may arise from unforeseen changes in traffic conditions. However, this stability does not extend to the full Cyprus sensitivity analysis, where a larger bus network is examined within a framework of more constrained planning options. These constraints include a limited number of available locations, fewer candidate chargers per location, and, consequently, reduced charging slot availability. This analysis underscores the critical role of planning flexibility in such models, as incorporating a wider range of planning options can significantly influence both the outcomes and the long-term resilience of the charging station network.

5. Conclusion

This article introduces a methodology that solves the bi-objective problem of optimal extensions of a network of charging stations that support the operation of electric buses. The methodology can be applied to real-world data and can derive decision support for stakeholders involved in the strategic planning of charging station networks for fleets of electric buses. Based on the principles of MILP and MOOP, the proposed method can take into consideration two main objectives: (i) the minimization of electric bus deadhead times, and (ii) the minimization of the monetary cost that is required for the installation and operation of chargers. In this way, this research can contribute to the planning of considerably sized charging station networks inside urban environments, where multiple stakeholders with different objectives are involved.

This article represents an incremental step in advancing the research literature on the CSLP, offering a modeling approach accompanied by two primary limitations. The first limitation is that the model considers two types of chargers: slow chargers and fast chargers. Although this scenario reflects the current practical reality in many cities, where decisions often involve choosing between older and slower types of chargers and newer charger types (with more power and less charging time), future scenarios may require the inclusion of multi-charger configurations. The second limitation pertains to the case studies, which assume that each bus requires recharging only once per day (i.e. one τ_k per bus k). While this assumption aligns with the prevalent practices enabled by modern battery and charging technologies, certain scenarios may necessitate minor modifications to the model to account for multiple charging sessions per day.

Based on our findings, several future research directions emerge. This approach considers three charging scenarios for the buses: (i) charging for the entire slot duration, (ii) stopping early upon reaching maximum capacity SOC_k^{max} , and (iii) applying a partial recharge strategy when a limited amount of energy is required to serve the remaining trips for they day. Future work could explore additional recharging strategies, such as opportunistic recharging, where the bus may be able to charge at any point in time for any amount of energy. With this proposed extension, the charging demand for the fleet of electric buses may be satisfied at even better Pareto optimal solutions with less monetary cost and deadhead time. Secondly, further research could investigate the integrated CSLP problem from the perspective of the energy management authority, focusing on the pricing strategies they offer to public transport operators. As demonstrated in this study, pricing decisions can influence the charging schedules of public transport operators. Modeling and analyzing optimal pricing values based on operational, economic, and environmental criteria would be a valuable next step. Lastly, while the proposed approach proves effective in medium-sized urban environments like Limassol, its scalability to larger areas can be challenging due to computational complexity (as shown in Section 4.3). Thus, developing heuristic or metaheuristic methods is essential to address larger-scale networks of buses and charging stations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dimitrios Rizopoulos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Konstantinos Gkiotsalitis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Fig. A.1. Price points considered for each demand period $f_3 \in F_3$ of the toy bus network in Manhattan, New York.

Table A.1
Nomenclature.

Sets	
\mathcal{V}	set of all possible charging station physical locations.
\mathcal{N}	set of all possible installation options for chargers.
\mathcal{N}_1	set of slow charger installation options.
\mathcal{N}_2	set of fast charger installation options.
\mathcal{N}_3	set of already installed slow chargers.
\mathcal{N}_4	set of already installed fast chargers.
\mathcal{N}_5	set of candidate slow chargers, to potentially be installed.
\mathcal{N}_6	set of candidate fast chargers, to potentially be installed.
\mathcal{F}_1	set of time slots for slow chargers.
\mathcal{F}_2	set of time slots for fast chargers.
\mathcal{F}_3	set of time slots for calculating demand charge.
\mathcal{K}	set of trips that need charging.
Parameters	
SOC_k	state of charge of trip k after its completion.
SOC_k^{\min}	minimum allowed state of charge of trip k .
SOC_k^{\max}	maximum allowed state of charge of trip k .
$c_{f_1}^s$	starting times for charging time slots of slow charging stations.
$c_{f_2}^h$	starting times for charging time slots of fast charging stations.
τ_k	time when trip k is completed.
p_k^s	latest time threshold for trip k to start charging at a slow charger.
p_k^h	latest time threshold for trip k to start charging at a fast charger.
m	a very small positive number.
M	a very large positive number.
e	battery consumption per traveled distance.
b_j	fixed cost of installing charger j , i.e., if close to the inverter, the cost is smaller.
b^{\max}	total amount of installation budget.
d_{kj}	minimum travel distance between the final stop of trip k and the potential charger location j .
t_{kj}	estimated deadhead time from the last stop of trip k and the location of the potential charger j .

(continued on next page)

Table A.1 (continued).

a_{kj}	binary parameter that equals to 1 if there exists a charger $j \in \mathcal{N}$ which is reachable from the last stop of trip k given its minimum state of charge, and 0 otherwise.
CP^s	The charging power in kilowatts (kW) for slow chargers.
CP^h	The charging power in kilowatts (kW) for fast chargers.
EC_{kj}^{\max}	The energy (kWh) that can be transferred from a charger j to the bus k during any time slot, if the bus k charges at charger j .
SME^s	The maximum energy (in kWh) that can be transferred from a <i>slow charger</i> to the bus during a slow charger time slot f_1 .
SME^s	The maximum energy (in kWh) that can be transferred from a <i>fast charger</i> to the bus during a fast charger time slot f_2 .
CC_{kj}^s	The matrix of parameters, which take the value of 1 if the bus serving trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges for the whole duration of any charging slot f_1 at charging outlet $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$. The parameter takes the value of 0 if the bus charges up to its full battery capacity.
CC_{kj}^h	The matrix of parameters, which take the value of 1 if the bus serving trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ charges for the whole duration of any charging slot f_2 at charging outlet $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$. The parameter takes the value of 0 if the bus charges up to its full battery capacity.
PEC_{kj}^s	The pre-calculated parameter for the amount of energy that can be transferred from slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ to bus k , without considering the opportunity for partial charging.
PEC_{kj}^h	The pre-calculated parameter for the amount of energy that can be transferred from fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ to bus k , without considering the opportunity for partial charging.
\widehat{PEC}_{kj}^s	The pre-calculated parameter for the amount of energy that can be transferred from slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ to bus k , after considering the partial recharge strategy and the remaining trips \mathcal{R} .
\widehat{PEC}_{kj}^h	The pre-calculated parameter for the amount of energy that can be transferred from fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ to bus k , after considering the partial recharge strategy and the remaining trips \mathcal{R} .
DCP^s	The maximum amount of energy per demand charge period f_3 for <i>slow chargers</i> .
DCP^h	The maximum amount of energy per demand charge period f_3 for <i>fast chargers</i> .
FCS_{kj}^s	The number of time periods f_3 within any respective charging time slot f_1 that consume energy equal to DCP^s , out of the total number of r^s slots within any f_1 that is chosen for the charging of k at j .
FCS_{kj}^h	The number of time periods f_3 within any respective charging time slot f_2 that consume energy equal to DCP^h , out of the total number of r^s slots within any f_2 that is chosen for the charging of k at j .
RE_{kj}^s	The amount of energy transferred from a charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ to a bus k during the time period $f_3 = FCS_{kj}^s + 1$.
RE_{kj}^h	The amount of energy transferred from a charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ to a bus k during the time period $f_3 = FCS_{kj}^h + 1$.
Decision Variables	
\mathbf{x}	$\mathbf{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_j, \dots, x_{ N }]^T$, where $x_j = 1$ if we decide to construct $j \in \mathcal{N}$ and $x_j = 0$ if not.
Q	0–1 matrix, where $q_{kj} = 1$ if the trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is assigned to charger j and 0 otherwise.
$u_{kjj_1}^s$	binary variables, where $u_{kjj_1}^s = 1$ if trip k starts charging at slow charging time slot f_1 at charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$.
$u_{kjj_2}^h$	binary variables, where $u_{kjj_2}^h = 1$ if trip k starts charging at fast charging time slot f_2 at charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$.
Variables	
\mathbf{y}	$\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_i, \dots, y_{ K }]^T$ deadheading time of trip $k \in \mathcal{K}$.
$EC_{kjj_1}^s$	The energy consumption of bus k at slow charger j and time slot f_1 .
$EC_{kjj_2}^h$	The energy consumption of bus k at fast charger j and time slot f_2 .
$DC_{kjj_3}^s$	The energy consumption of bus k at slow charger j and time slot f_3 .
$DC_{kjj_3}^h$	The energy consumption of bus k at fast charger j and time slot f_3 .
DEC_{f_3}	The energy consumption of all chargers $j \in \mathcal{N}$ for time slot f_3 .
$UD_{f_3}^s$	Binary variable that takes the value of 1 if any bus k charges at slow charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_1$ at slot f_3 .
$UD_{f_3}^h$	Binary variable that takes the value of 1 if any bus k charges at fast charger $j \in \mathcal{N}_2$ at slot f_3 .
$IP_{f_3}^s$	Total power required to charge bus fleet coming from slow chargers during period f_3 .
$IP_{f_3}^h$	Total power required to charge bus fleet coming from fast chargers during period f_3 .
TIP_{f_3}	Total power required for charging buses from fast chargers during period f_3 .
IP^{\max}	Maximum power required for the charging of electric buses across all time slots $f_3 \in \mathcal{F}_3$.

Table A.2

Values of temporal parameters ($\tau_k, P1_k, P2_k$) and SOC_k for buses of the Manhattan toy network. Values of temporal parameters are in minutes past midnight, assuming continuous time representation, while SOC_k is in kilowatt-hours (kWh).

Bus trip	τ_k	$P1_k$	$P2_k$	SOC_k	Bus trip	τ_k	$P1_k$	$P2_k$	SOC_k
1	732	1272	1272	142.1	31	1438	1978	1978	159.7
2	769	1309	1309	77.6	32	1491	2031	2031	151.6
3	800	1340	1340	103.9	33	735	1275	1275	131.3
4	824	1364	1364	98.4	34	767	1307	1307	177.2
5	852	1392	1392	152.3	35	795	1335	1335	114.7
6	872	1412	1412	146.1	36	824	1364	1364	133.0
7	897	1437	1437	168.7	37	847	1387	1387	162.1
8	919	1459	1459	84.1	38	878	1418	1418	139.9
9	948	1488	1488	119.3	39	907	1447	1447	165.5
10	965	1505	1505	78.1	40	932	1472	1472	135.6
11	986	1526	1526	98.0	41	973	1513	1513	149.0
12	1002	1542	1542	128.1	42	995	1535	1535	79.8
13	1014	1554	1554	77.8	43	1019	1559	1559	98.9
14	1029	1569	1569	95.9	44	1052	1592	1592	105.4
15	1049	1589	1589	143.2	45	1082	1622	1622	83.4
16	1069	1609	1609	132.2	46	1108	1648	1648	99.4
17	1079	1619	1619	98.1	47	1129	1669	1669	85.6
18	1092	1632	1632	136.9	48	1146	1686	1686	104.2
19	1106	1646	1646	160.0	49	1168	1708	1708	141.7
20	1115	1655	1655	75.7	50	1188	1728	1728	113.3
21	1133	1673	1673	159.6	51	1207	1747	1747	113.9
22	1148	1688	1688	148.3	52	1236	1776	1776	97.0
23	1166	1706	1706	110.7	53	1257	1797	1797	103.0
24	1184	1724	1724	91.3	54	1280	1820	1820	173.3
25	1212	1752	1752	175.5	55	1301	1841	1841	143.0
26	1242	1782	1782	110.3	56	1331	1871	1871	139.0
27	1264	1804	1804	84.7	57	1368	1908	1908	93.0
28	1302	1842	1842	85.2	58	1406	1946	1946	151.6
29	1344	1884	1884	164.0	59	1441	1981	1981	92.2
30	1391	1931	1931	138.4	60	1503	2043	2043	114.8

Table A.3

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 2 of the toy network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 231.56$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 331,269.4$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments										
			13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	51	51
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	–	–
1	Fast	4	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	–	–	–	54
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	30	30	36	36	15	15	16	16	–	–
2	Fast	8	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	47	–	21	–
2	Slow	9	–	3	3	1	1	39	39	23	23	–	–
2	Slow	11	–	33	33	5	5	31	31	17	17	–	–
3	Slow	15	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	19	19	25	25
3	Fast	16	–	–	6	–	13	12	20	22	24	27	53
3	Fast	18	–	–	7	8	10	14	–	18	26	28	29
6	Slow	33	–	–	–	–	–	41	41	–	–	49	49
6	Fast	34	–	32	34	37	–	40	43	–	48	50	52

Table A.4

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 3 of the toy network with $\vartheta_1 = 233.52$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\vartheta_2 = 301,269.385$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments										
			13:00–	14:00–	15:00–	16:00–	17:00–	18:00–	19:00–	20:00–	21:00–	22:00–	23:00–
			14:00	15:00	16:00	17:00	18:00	19:00	20:00	21:00	22:00	23:00	24:00
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	51	51
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	30	30	1	1	15	15	17	17	–	–
2	Fast	8	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	47	–	–	16
2	Slow	9	–	3	3	5	5	31	31	21	21	–	–
2	Slow	11	–	33	33	36	36	39	39	23	23	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	–	–	10	14	20	–	26	25	54
3	Fast	16	–	–	7	8	12	–	–	19	24	28	29
3	Fast	18	–	–	6	–	13	–	18	22	–	27	53
6	Slow	31	–	–	–	–	–	41	41	–	–	49	49
6	Fast	34	–	32	34	37	–	40	43	–	48	50	52

Table A.5

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 4 of the toy network with $\vartheta_1 = 239.07$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\vartheta_2 = 271,275.3$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments										
			13:00–	14:00–	15:00–	16:00–	17:00–	18:00–	19:00–	20:00–	21:00–	22:00–	23:00–
			14:00	15:00	16:00	17:00	18:00	19:00	20:00	21:00	22:00	23:00	24:00
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	–	–
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	51	51
2	Slow	7	–	30	30	1	1	15	15	–	–	16	16
2	Fast	8	2	3	35	9	11	38	42	47	–	21	23
2	Slow	9	–	4	4	5	5	39	39	–	–	–	–
2	Slow	11	–	33	33	36	36	31	31	17	17	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	6	8	13	–	–	22	49	28	54
3	Fast	16	–	–	7	–	12	14	18	19	24	25	29
3	Fast	18	–	–	–	–	10	–	20	–	26	27	53
6	Fast	32	–	32	34	37	–	40	43	41	48	50	52

Table A.6

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 5 of the toy network with $\vartheta_1 = 249.08$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\vartheta_2 = 251,272.34$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments										
			13:00–	14:00–	15:00–	16:00–	17:00–	18:00–	19:00–	20:00–	21:00–	22:00–	23:00–
			14:00	15:00	16:00	17:00	18:00	19:00	20:00	21:00	22:00	23:00	24:00
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	51	51
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	25	25
2	Slow	7	–	3	3	36	36	15	15	17	17	–	–
2	Fast	8	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	47	–	16	53
2	Slow	9	–	33	33	5	5	39	39	23	23	–	–
2	Slow	11	–	30	30	1	1	31	31	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	7	–	13	14	18	22	26	28	54
3	Fast	16	–	–	6	8	10	12	20	19	24	27	29
6	Slow	31	–	–	–	–	–	41	41	–	–	49	49
6	Fast	32	–	32	34	37	–	40	43	–	48	50	52

Table A.7

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 6 of the toy network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 256.83$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 221,277.71$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00	
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	50	50
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	51	51
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	25	25
2	Slow	7	–	30	30	5	5	39	39	47	47	–	–	–
2	Fast	8	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	–	–	21	53	–
2	Slow	9	–	3	3	36	36	31	31	17	17	16	16	–
2	Slow	11	–	33	33	1	1	15	15	23	23	–	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	7	8	13	14	18	19	26	27	29	–
3	Fast	16	–	–	6	–	10	12	20	22	24	28	54	–
6	Fast	34	–	32	34	37	–	40	43	41	48	49	52	–

Table A.8

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 7 of the toy network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 291.08$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 219,871.98$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00	
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	46	46	25	25
1	Slow	3	–	3	3	–	–	–	–	–	45	45	49	49
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	51	51
2	Slow	7	–	33	33	5	5	15	15	–	–	–	–	–
2	Fast	8	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	47	–	21	53	–
2	Slow	9	–	30	30	31	31	16	16	17	17	–	–	–
2	Slow	11	–	1	1	36	36	39	39	23	23	–	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	6	7	10	14	20	22	24	28	54	–
3	Fast	18	–	–	–	8	13	41	18	19	26	27	29	–
6	Fast	36	–	32	34	37	12	40	43	–	48	50	52	–

Table A.9

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 8 of the toy network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 312.37$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 201,290.35$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00	
1	Slow	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	24	24	52	52
1	Slow	3	–	–	–	–	–	41	41	46	46	50	50	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	44	44	48	48	–
2	Slow	7	–	30	30	36	36	31	31	17	17	21	21	–
2	Slow	9	–	3	3	5	5	39	39	–	–	16	16	–
2	Slow	11	–	33	33	1	1	15	15	47	47	–	–	–
2	Fast	12	2	4	35	9	11	38	42	45	23	51	53	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	6	37	13	12	20	22	25	28	29	–
3	Fast	16	–	–	7	8	10	14	18	19	26	27	54	–
6	Slow	35	–	32	32	34	34	40	40	43	43	49	49	–

Table A.10

Values of temporal parameters (τ_k , $P1_k$, $P2_k$) and SOC_k for buses of the Limassol case study. Values of temporal parameters are in minutes past midnight, assuming continuous time representation, while SOC_k is in kilowatt-hours (kWh).

Bus trip	τ_k	$P1_k$	$P2_k$	SOC_k	Bus trip	τ_k	$P1_k$	$P2_k$	SOC_k
1	800	920	920	141.88	18	795	915	915	134.09
2	874	994	994	70.78	19	910	1030	1030	153.27
3	1030	1150	1150	99.08	20	1049	1169	1169	68.87
4	1189	1309	1309	89.36	21	1180	1300	1300	153.66
5	780	900	900	150.11	22	760	880	880	144.79
6	904	1024	1024	144.73	23	800	920	920	107.3
7	1065	1185	1185	159.17	24	884	1004	1004	87.74
8	1184	1304	1304	75.28	25	960	1080	1080	167.28
9	819	939	939	114.06	26	1034	1154	1154	109.51
10	944	1064	1064	76.64	27	1139	1259	1259	84.56
11	1030	1150	1150	89.19	28	1214	1334	1334	84.58
12	1174	1294	1294	124.34	29	659	779	779	157.96
13	1215	1335	1335	71.25	30	819	939	939	132.62
14	779	899	899	90.23	31	875	995	995	157.26
15	859	979	979	142.49	32	790	910	910	146.9
16	989	1109	1109	126.41	33	865	985	985	131.06
17	1060	1180	1180	91.49	34	1080	1200	1200	169.63

Table A.11

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 5 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 83.01$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 165,066.14$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	29	29	30	30	10	10	20	20	27
1	Slow	3	–	–	14	14	2	2	26	26	34	34	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	9	9	15	15	16	16	4	4	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	5	–	24	–	11	17	12	8	–	–
4	Fast	24	–	–	1	32	33	6	–	3	–	–	–	–
6	Fast	34	–	22	23	31	–	–	25	7	–	–	28	–

Table A.12

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 6 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 85.93$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 162,276.93$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	29	29	1	1	2	2	–	–	34
1	Fast	2	–	14	32	33	24	10	3	20	–	–	–	–
1	Slow	3	–	–	30	30	15	15	16	16	27	27	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	9	9	6	6	26	26	4	4	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	14	–	–	5	–	–	–	17	11	8	12	–	–
6	Fast	34	–	22	–	23	31	–	25	7	–	–	28	–

Table A.13

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 7 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 96.01$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 143,671.63$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
			1	Slow	1	29	29	30	30	10	10	16	16	27
1	Slow	3	–	–	9	9	15	15	26	26	34	34	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	14	14	2	2	20	20	4	4	13	13
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Fast	18	–	22	–	5	24	–	17	11	12	8	–	–
4	Fast	20	–	–	32	1	33	6	7	3	–	–	–	–
6	Slow	35	–	–	23	23	31	31	25	25	–	–	28	28

Table A.14

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 8 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 103.7$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 142,277.82$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	29	29	9	9	10	10	26	26	34	34	13	13
1	Slow	3	–	–	32	32	15	15	16	16	27	27	–	–
1	Fast	4	–	14	30	33	24	6	–	3	–	–	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	1	1	2	2	20	20	4	4	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
3	Slow	13	–	–	–	–	–	–	17	17	12	12	–	–
6	Fast	34	–	22	23	5	31	25	11	7	8	28	–	–

Table A.15

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 9 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 115.98$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 122,277.62$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	29	29	9	9	10	10	20	20	34	34	–	–
1	Slow	3	–	–	14	14	15	15	26	26	4	4	13	13
1	Slow	5	–	–	30	30	2	2	16	16	27	27	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	11	11	21	21	–	–
3	Slow	15	–	–	5	5	24	24	17	17	12	12	–	–
4	Fast	24	–	22	32	1	33	6	3	7	–	–	–	–
6	Slow	33	–	–	23	23	31	31	25	25	8	8	28	28

Table A.16

The assignment of bus trips to chargers and time windows for the Pareto optimal solution 10 for the Limassol bus network with $\mathcal{O}_1 = 125.03$ (minutes, deadhead time) and $\mathcal{O}_2 = 112,278.89$ (dollars, monetary cost).

Location Selected	Charger type	Charger	Time Slots for Charging Assignments											
			12:00–13:00	13:00–14:00	14:00–15:00	15:00–16:00	16:00–17:00	17:00–18:00	18:00–19:00	19:00–20:00	20:00–21:00	21:00–22:00	22:00–23:00	23:00–24:00
1	Slow	1	29	29	9	9	6	6	3	3	27	27	13	13
1	Slow	3	–	–	1	1	2	2	7	7	4	4	–	–
1	Slow	5	–	–	30	30	15	15	20	20	34	34	–	–
1	Fast	6	–	14	32	33	24	10	16	26	–	–	–	–
2	Slow	7	–	–	18	18	19	19	–	–	21	21	–	–
6	Fast	32	–	22	23	5	31	25	17	11	8	12	28	–

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